

Deliverable 1.1

Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models

Aristotle University of
Thessaloniki (AUTH)
22/12/2022

**DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH**

PROJECT INFORMATION

PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON-CSA
PROJECT NUMBER	101060504
START DAY	1 September 2022
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	D1.1: Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models
WORK PACKAGE	Work Package 1
TASK	Task 1.2
AUTHORS (Organisation)	Efstratios Stylianidis (AUPh), Maria Partalidou (AUPh), Dimitrios Natos (AUPh), Asterios Theofilou (AUPh), Alexandros Skondras (AUPh)
REVIEWERS	Pinelopi Kaslama (WR), James Gaffey (MTU), Robert Ludgate (MTU), Christos Politis (QPL), Margarita Angelidou (QPL), Kallitsa Pantazi (RCM), Eleni Pappa (RCM), Dimitrios Vlachos (RCM), Anthoula Papadopoulou (RCM), Sergi Costa (BPRO), Mar Cátedra Cerón (CAP), Samir Sayadi Gmada (IFA), Marta Macías Aragonés (CTA), Carmen Ronchel Barreno (CTA)
DATE	22/12/2022

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public, fully open	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Changes	Responsible partner
1.1	02/12/2022	Initial draft	AUTh
1.2	14/12/2022	Final version after partners quality review	AUTh
1.3	22/12/2022	Final version for submission to COO	AUTh
2.0	22/12/2022	Final version for submission to EC	QPL

LEGAL NOTICE

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

© ROBIN Consortium, 2022

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	9
2	INTRODUCTION.....	10
3	METHODOLOGY	11
4	BIOECONOMY GOVERNANCE MODELS ACROSS EUROPE	12
4.1	European regions with bioeconomy related strategies/models	15
4.2	Bioeconomy related strategies/models in European regions	17
4.3	Analysis of commonalities and divergences	17
5	CASE STUDIES PRESENTATION	22
5.1	Case 1: Green Synergy Cluster (Cluster Zelena Sinergiya).....	23
5.2	Case 2: Resilient Thessaloniki	28
5.3	Case 3: Circular Bio-based Delta	33
5.4	Case 4: Regional Innovation Strategy Sachsen-Anhalt 2014 – 2020 34	
5.5	Case 5: BioökonomieREVIER.....	36
5.6	Case 6: Bavaria´s Bioeconomy Strategy.....	38
5.7	Case 7: Alliance Plant ³	40
5.8	Case 8: Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy	41
5.9	Case 9: Bioeconomy Strategy of Catalonia	46
5.10	Case 10: Circular Economy Strategy	49
5.11	Case 11: Plan to boost to the agri-food bioeconomy.....	51
5.12	Case 12: Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Plan 2024.....	53
5.13	Case 13: Irish Bioeconomy Foundation	55
5.14	Case 14: North Sweden Cleantech.....	57
5.15	Case 15: The Bioeconomy Strategy of the Inland Region 2017-2024 59	
5.16	Case 16: The Arctic Smart & Circular Economy Cluster	62
5.17	Case 17: Bio-based Circular Economy Action Plan	64
5.18	Case 18: Circular Economy Strategy Luxembourg	65
5.19	Case 19: South Bohemian Association for Bioeconomy.....	67
5.20	Case 20: Regional municipal biomass project on Pol'ana.....	69
6	TYPOLGY OF CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY GOVERNANCE MODELS.....	72
6.1	Transformation paths	72
6.2	Enabling function.....	73

6.3	Safeguarding function.....	73
6.4	Penta helix.....	74
6.5	Transition process.....	75
6.6	Territorial aspects of the governance model.....	75
6.7	Statutory level.....	75
6.8	Decision making, voting mechanisms dispute resolution processes	
	76	
6.9	Driver Measures.....	76
6.10	Support measures and tools.....	76
6.11	Typology Matrix.....	77
7	CONCLUSIONS.....	78
8	REFERENCES.....	79
9	APPENDIX.....	80

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Long Term sustainable development Source: European Commission, (2018)]	12
Figure 2: EU Regions with bioeconomy strategies [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]	14
Figure 3: Governance Structure of Bioeast [Source: https://bioeast.eu/]	15
Figure 4: EU regions with bioeconomy strategies [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)].....	17
Figure 5: Sectors addressed by regional bioeconomy models [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]	18
Figure 6: Biomass resources addressed in dedicated and regional strategies with a strong bioeconomy element [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)].....	19
Figure 7: Biomass resources addressed in regions [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)].....	20
Figure 8: Policy measures included in regional bioeconomy models [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)].....	21
Figure 9 EU map with NUTS1 and NUTS2 territorial levels of the case studies collected, and case studies presented.....	22
Figure 10: Penta helix [Source: Naudet and Marrazzo (2021)]	75

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: EU-27 regions with bioeconomy related strategies [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]	16
Table 2: EU-27 regions with bioeconomy related strategies [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]	16
Table 3: Bio-based transformation paths.....	72
Table 4: Enabling Governance Mechanisms.....	73
Table 5: Opportunities and Risks of Bioeconomic Transformation [Source: Dietz et al., 2018].....	74
Table 6: Typology Matrix	77

ABBREVIATIONS

AUTH	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
CEE	Central and Eastern European Countries
EU	European Union
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
JRC	Joint Research Centre
NUTS	Nomenclature des Unités territoriales statistiques
QH	Quadruple Helix
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
S3s	Smart Specialization Strategies

1 Executive summary

The circular bioeconomy is based on the idea of applying biological principles and processes in the economy to replace fossil-based raw materials with bio-based materials, principles, and processes. The innovative and sustainable use of bio-based resources, through a bio-based transformation of the economy, provides opportunities for sustainability, enabling the achievement of various Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This requires governance structures and models that ensure the development of sustainable, bio-based transformations.

Governance has two important functions for a sustainable circular bioeconomy: First, a safeguarding function, i.e., there is a need for explicit safeguards of economic, social, and ecological sustainability through appropriate governance approaches. Second, an enabling function. In addition to ensuring sustainability, the governance framework also has the task of ensuring fair competitive conditions for bioeconomy processes and products in the first place, thus enabling efficient decisions between alternative technologies and biogenic and non-biogenic resources on markets.

The methodological approach employed to collect data on regional bioeconomy models was a literature review through desk research and a data collection survey through partners of the ROBIN consortium. The desk research was based on policy documents, material from previous H2020 projects, reports by the JRC, and academic papers. The literature review investigates potential assessment methods and evidence on the effectiveness and robustness of existing governance schemes in the EU. The data collection survey was conducted with the coordination of AUTH team and the assistance of all partners. The data collected comprised of 61 circular bioeconomy models and was compiled in an MS Excel spreadsheet for further analysis and data was analyzed to identify the 20 circular bioeconomy model case studies to be further analyzed. The dataset with the complete list of models is available and complements this deliverable.

The deliverable presents an overview of regional circular bioeconomy governance strategies and models in the EU-27 and a typology of regional bioeconomy governance models along ten dimensions, based on a sample of 20 circular bioeconomy case studies. The typology distinguishes four bio-based transformation paths and two main governance functions, enabling governance and constraining governance. The typology allows the classification of present and future circular bioeconomy governance models. Based solely on the three enabling governance mechanisms and the five constraining governance mechanisms identified, over fifteen (>15) types of circular bioeconomy governance models can be distinguished, satisfying the requisite KPI objective.

Our results corroborate previous findings that many regions have set the goal of developing and expanding their bioeconomies and local governments are providing comprehensive political support to their bioeconomies to achieve this goal. Currently, regions are highly active in addressing this enabling governance challenge. However, our results show that the political management of conflicting goals has not yet reached the same level of attention.

The typology developed in this deliverable is directly linked with Task 1.3 and will be employed in Deliverable 1.2 Good Governance Practices, to classify the list of good practices of regional governments supporting local operators and innovation developers via appropriate business models and social measures.

2 Introduction

The bioeconomy is based on the idea of applying biological principles and processes in the economy to replace fossil-based raw materials with bio-based materials, principles, and processes (Dietz et al., 2018). The innovative and sustainable use of bio-based resources, through a bio-based transformation of the economy, provides opportunities for sustainability, enabling the achievement of various Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This requires governance structures and models that ensure the development of sustainable, bio-based transformations (Von Braun and Birner, 2016).

The term “governance” describes in general terms a system of control and regulation that includes state intervention, but also rules governing the interaction of private actors (markets, associations, actor networks such as clusters) (Thran and Moesenfechtel, 2022). Various forms of governance can be found in the literature that structure the interactions of the actors, markets, interest groups and clusters, as well as negotiation processes for informal rules. Governance is the process by which societies adapt their rules to new challenges and it has a substantial dimension, a procedural dimension, and a structural dimension (Dietz et al., 2018). The substantial dimension determines what are the governance rules, the procedural dimension describes how the governance rules are developed and the structural dimension describes what are the procedural rules and institutions that determine rulemaking, as well as how the rules are implemented and enforced and how conflicts over rules are resolved.

Governance has two important functions for a sustainable circular bioeconomy (Thran and Moesenfechtel, 2022). First, a safeguarding function, i.e., there is a need for explicit safeguards of economic, social, and ecological sustainability through appropriate governance approaches. To initiate and properly steer the path transition from a traditional economy structure to a circular bioeconomy structure, an effective governance framework is essential that consistently guides the political and economic actors. Bioeconomy concepts must therefore be safeguarded with sustainability principles for a comprehensive path transition from the current “throughput and sink economy” based on non-renewable materials to a circular bioeconomy based on renewable and recyclable resources. Second, an enabling function. In addition to ensuring sustainability, the governance framework also has the task of ensuring fair competitive conditions for bioeconomy processes and products in the first place, thus enabling efficient decisions between alternative technologies and biogenic and non-biogenic resources on markets (Thran and Moesenfechtel, 2022).

Governmental governance models face significant challenges in adequately promoting the pathway transition to a circular bioeconomy while providing effective sustainability assurance. One important reason for this is information problems arising from uncertainties about economic, environmental, and social impacts of multiple and diverse bioeconomy value chains (McCormick and Kautto, 2013 in Thran and Moesenfechtel, 2022). For the establishment of a sustainable bioeconomy, it is important to disclose conflicting goals and to discuss prioritization (Thran and Moesenfechtel, 2022).

The deliverable is structured as follows: the next section (Section 3) describes the methodology employed, followed by an overview of regional bioeconomy governance models across Europe (Section 4). Section 5 presents the 20 case study governance models selected, Section 6 presents a typology of regional circular bioeconomy governance models and analyzes the results of the 20 case studies. Finally, Section 7 concludes.

3 Methodology

The following definition of a bioeconomy strategy is employed in the analysis: “Bioeconomy strategy is the set of regulatory frameworks used by official authorities in describing how policy goals and objectives may be achieved. It includes strategies, action plans, roadmaps, resource management plans, that promote the development of bio-based value chains as part of a sustainable and circular bioeconomy.” In the analysis conducted in this deliverable, models that are not part of an official bioeconomy strategy have also been considered.

The methodological approach employed to collect data on regional bioeconomy models was a literature review through desk research and data collection through partners of the ROBIN consortium. The desk research was based on documents and other sources available online. The literature review also investigates potential assessment methods and evidence on the effectiveness and robustness of existing governance schemes in the EU through the development of a typology of governance models. The data collection survey was conducted with the coordination of AUTH team and the assistance of all partners of the consortium. The data collected comprised of 61 models and was compiled in an MS Excel spreadsheet for further analysis and data was analyzed to identify the 20 model case studies to be further analyzed. The dataset with the complete list of models is available and complements this deliverable.

The research focused on identifying models of the bioeconomy and circular bioeconomy in the regions of EU-27 and EU Associated countries. The research predominantly focused on active or planned models and strategies, but also considered some models that have been recently completed. Although the focus is at the regional level, some national models are included, either for small countries or in cases where no regional model was available.

Out of the 61 models initially collected, several of them were excluded due to incomplete or missing data. In addition, models that did not mention support measures and models that were national, except for small countries, were also eliminated, as the focus of the analysis is at the sub-national, regional, level.

4 Bioeconomy governance models across Europe

The 2018 EU Bioeconomy Strategy, originally adopted in 2012 and updated in 2018, provides a coherent framework that cuts across various sectors and policies, allowing to build synergies, address tradeoffs and deliver sustainability across various policy and sectoral objectives.

Figure 1: Long Term sustainable development Source: European Commission, (2018)]

The European Commission's Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy published this year the final report of a study that maps and analyses the deployment of strategies related to the bioeconomy, at the regional level, in the EU-27. The study contains up-to-date information on regulatory frameworks in place or under development as of November 2021 (Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak, 2022). The study focused on the predominant sub-national NUTS level in each country, on what is usually classified as the 'regional level' in between national and local levels, typically NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 territorial levels. The nomenclature of territorial units for statistics (Nomenclature des Unités territoriales statistiques – NUTS) is a geographical system, according to which the territory of the European Union is divided into hierarchical levels. The three hierarchical levels are known as NUTS 1, NUTS 2 and NUTS 3.

The results of the study indicate that 194 regions in the EU-27 (at the NUTS 1, NUTS 2 or NUTS 3 level) have, or are in the process of implementing, a strategy aimed at the bioeconomy. According to the analysis, 28 regions have a dedicated bioeconomy strategy in place and one region is in the process of implementing one. Furthermore, 62 regions have strategies with a strong focus on the bioeconomy and 7 additional regions are in the process of implementing such a strategy. Finally, 94 regions have strategies with a minimal emphasis on the bioeconomy and another two regions are in the process of implementing such types of strategies.

Some countries, such as Belgium, France, Italy, and the Netherlands have developed bioeconomy related strategic frameworks for all regions (Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak, 2022). Overall, a total of 359 bioeconomy related strategic frameworks exist in the EU-27.

An initial mapping of bioeconomy strategies at the European level was presented in the 2018 EU Action Plan for the Bioeconomy Strategy (European Commission, 2018). In that report, the majority (207) of the 210 territorial units analyzed, included bioeconomy related aspects in their research and innovation plans. Since then, the EU Joint Research Center (JRC) has been mapping the progress of EU member-states in developing and implementing policies aimed at the bioeconomy. In 2022, the European Commission's Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy published an updated report of a study that maps and analyses the deployment of strategies related to the bioeconomy, at the regional level, in the EU-27. The study contains the most up-to-date information on regulatory frameworks in place or under development and the following section draws heavily from the results presented in the report.

There are currently 194 regions in the EU-27 that have or are in the process of implementing a dedicated bioeconomy strategy, 62 regions have strategies with a strong bioeconomy focus and 94 regions have strategies with some bioeconomy focus (Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak, 2022). Italy is the country with the largest number of regions with bioeconomy strategies (21), followed by Sweden (20), France (18), Spain (17), Finland (16) and Poland (16). Additionally, all regions in Belgium, France, Italy, and the Netherlands have developed bioeconomy related strategic frameworks. Furthermore, France, Italy, Finland, Belgium, and Sweden have the highest shares of regional strategies with a clear and strong bioeconomy focus (Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak, 2022). Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022) identify a total of 359 bioeconomy related strategies that are either published or under development in the EU-27 and of those, 334 strategic frameworks are in the form of strategies, action plans, roadmaps, or resource management plans with the remaining 25 being under development.

Figure 2: EU Regions with bioeconomy strategies [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]

It is of interest to note that most strategic frameworks are very recent, with a significant number of them published in the last year, 2021. This may be explained by the fact that the new Multiannual Financial Framework started in the same year and regional strategies may be aligned to benefit from the new EU programmes (2021-2027).

Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022) estimated that approximately a third of regional bioeconomy strategies address the supply side of biomass, mostly through agriculture, forestry, and organic waste, another one third of regional bioeconomy strategies address biomass processing and conversion to bioenergy and biofuels, agri-food and construction, and a very small number of strategies address all sectors of the bioeconomy value chain.

Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022) also determine some patterns of how the bioeconomy strategies are implemented or embedded in combination with other priorities. They determine that in Spain, the bioeconomy strategy is often included in circular economy strategies, whereas in Italy, it is often included in sustainable development strategies. In Finland, the bioeconomy strategy is included in the Regional Development Plans and in many S3s (Smart Specialization Strategies) and in climate action plans.

The presence of a regional bioeconomy strategy is determined by two main factors. First, if the country is large and decentralized, then regional bioeconomy strategies are mostly present. In small countries, such as Luxembourg, Malta and Cyprus, there are no regional bioeconomy strategies, due to their small size, and this was also evident from the data collected by the ROBIN project. Second, if the country has a national bioeconomy strategy, then the bioeconomy strategy at the regional level is often embedded in wider strategic frameworks. European Territorial Cooperation Programmes (Interreg) seem to have played a significant role in the development of regional bioeconomy strategies. Bioeast is another initiative with a similar role, promoting the development of the bioeconomy in eleven central and eastern European (CEE) countries.

Figure 3: Governance Structure of Bioeast [Source: <https://bioeast.eu/>]

Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022) note that the definition of the bioeconomy is not the same across the EU. To this, the different languages seem to have a different understanding of the bioeconomy.

Following is a two-fold brief description of European regions with bioeconomy related strategies and the bioeconomy related strategies identified in European regions (Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak, 2022).

4.1 European regions with bioeconomy related strategies/models

Currently, there are 194 regions identified in the EU-27 that have or are in the process of implementing a strategy focused on the bioeconomy (Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak, 2022). The following table presents the available documentation on bioeconomy strategies (Table 1 & 2). Italy has the highest number of regions with bioeconomy related strategies, followed by Sweden, France, Spain, Finland, and Poland. These six countries are actively promoting the bioeconomy through regional, strategic plans. On the other hand, data show that six EU Member-States have no bioeconomy-relevant strategies, namely Bulgaria, Cyprus, Estonia, Luxembourg, Malta, and Slovenia, although our analysis shows that this is not true. More specifically, Bulgaria does have a regional bioeconomy model. Luxemburg, Cyprus and Malta have national bioeconomy-relevant strategies.

Table 1: EU-27 regions with bioeconomy related strategies [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]

Country	Regions with published strategic frameworks	Regions with strategic frameworks under development	Regions with strategic frameworks TOTAL	Pre-dominant NUTS level of strategic frameworks per country	Total number of regions per country*
AT	8	-	8	NUTS 2	9
BE	3	-	3	NUTS 1	3
BG	-	-	-	-	-
CY	-	-	-	-	-
CZ	11	-	11	NUTS 3	14
DE	13	-	13	NUTS 1	16 NUTS1 and 1 NUTS2 = 17
DK	4	-	4	NUTS 2	5
EE	-	-	-	-	-
EL	2	-	2	NUTS 2	13
ES	14	3	17	NUTS 2	19 NUTS2 and 1 NUTS3 = 20
FI	16	-	16	NUTS 3	19
FR	18	-	18	NUTS 1	13 NUTS1 and 5 NUTS2 = 18
HR	1	-	1	NUTS 3	21
HU	10	-	10	NUTS 3	20

Table 2: EU-27 regions with bioeconomy related strategies [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]

Country	Regions with published strategic frameworks	Regions with strategic frameworks under development	Regions with strategic frameworks TOTAL	Pre-dominant NUTS level of strategic frameworks per country	Total number of regions per country*
IE	7	-	7	NUTS 3	8
IT	19	2	21	NUTS 2	21
LT	1	-	1	NUTS 3	10
LU	-	-	-	-	-
LV	2	-	2	NUTS 3	6
MT	-	-	-	-	-
NL	5	-	5	NUTS 1	4 NUTS1 and 1 NUTS2 = 5
PL	15	1	16	NUTS 2	1 NUTS1 and 17 NUTS2
PT	7	-	7	NUTS 2	7 NUTS2 and 1 NUTS3 = 8
RO	7	-	7	NUTS 2	8
SE	16	4	20	NUTS 3	21
SI	-	-	-	-	-
SK	5	-	5	NUTS 3	8
Total	184	10	194	--	272

4.2 Bioeconomy related strategies/models in European regions

Some additional patterns regarding the regional circular bioeconomy models are present. The following figure presents the EU regions with bioeconomy strategies. In Spain and Portugal, the bioeconomy is often embedded in circular economy strategies, whereas in Finland, the bioeconomy is covered in the Regional Development Plans and in S3s (Smart Specialization Strategies). In Poland, the bioeconomy is in either Regional Development Plans or in R&I (Research and Innovation) strategies. Finally in Hungary, the bioeconomy is identified in territorial development plans (Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak, 2022).

Figure 4: EU regions with bioeconomy strategies [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]

4.3 Analysis of commonalities and divergences

The EU Bioeconomy Strategy defines five goals: ensure food and nutrition security, manage natural resources sustainably, reduce dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, limit and adapt to climate change and to strengthen European competitiveness and create jobs. Haarich and

Kirchmayr-Novak (2022) analyzed 349 strategies and concluded that of these bioeconomy strategies 77% have an emphasis on the management of natural resources sustainably, followed by 68% of strategies also focusing on reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources. Additionally, 63% of bioeconomy strategies aim at strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs, 57% have the goal of limiting and adapting to climate change and only 27% have the goal of ensuring food and nutrition safety, clearly showing the convergence of goal orientation in Europe.

As aforementioned, most bioeconomy strategies have been published in the last two years, with the highest number in 2021, in line with the commencement of the Multiannual Financial Framework and the timeframe of the new EU Program period (2021-2027).

The analysis of sectors and value chains showcases that approximately one third of bioeconomy models focus on agriculture, forestry, and organic waste (Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak, 2022). An additional one third of bioeconomy models focus on biomass processing and conversion, bioenergy, agri-food sector, or construction. Sectors such as fisheries and aquaculture as well as tourism and transport are not included in a significant number of bioeconomy models.

Figure 5: Sectors addressed by regional bioeconomy models [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]

The resources addressed by the bioeconomy strategies and models analyzed by Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022) are presented in Figure 6. Forestry-based biomass, agricultural biomass and agricultural residues form a significant part of biomass resources addressed, in line with the sectors where most bioeconomy models focus. In addition, different types of waste are addressed (Household waste, food waste, industrial waste/biomass, sewage sludge, wastewater).

D1.1: Typology of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Models 22/12/2022

Figure 6: Biomass resources addressed in dedicated and regional strategies with a strong bioeconomy element [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]

The following map illustrates the EU regions and the biomass resources addressed in each region.

Figure 7: Biomass resources addressed in regions [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]

Finally, a diverse array of policies is included in the bioeconomy models analyzed by Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022), and although explicit information was not included for all policies, results indicate that most common policy was the funding of research and innovation (R&I) and governance measures. Additionally, policies aimed at collaboration, either through facilitation of bottom-up initiatives or measures to enable multi-stakeholder involvement and dialogue. Other policy measures include promotion measures aimed at raising awareness and providing information on the bioeconomy, promotion of bioeconomy-specific research centers and demonstration facilities (infrastructure), training, and support for stimulating demand (Fig 8).

Figure 8: Policy measures included in regional bioeconomy models [Source: Haarich and Kirchmayr-Novak (2022)]

5 Case studies presentation

Figure 9 EU map with NUTS1 and NUTS2 territorial levels of the case studies collected, and case studies presented

Following, is the presentation of the 20 case studies employed in the analysis and the construction of the typology of circular bioeconomy governance models across Europe.

5.1 Case 1: Green Synergy Cluster (Cluster Zelena Sinergiya)

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Green Synergy Cluster Cluster Zelena sinergiya
Organization name	Green Synergy Cluster Cluster Zelena sinergiya
Website(s)	https://greensynergycluster.eu/ https://clustercollaboration.eu/content/green-synergy-cluster
Region/Geographical scale	Bulgaria / South-Central
Year	2011
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	<p>GREEN SYNERGY cluster is established in 2011. as a non-profit organization.</p> <p>The cluster brings together and coordinates the knowledge and experience of companies, research entities and public authorities with an interest in the green transition.</p> <p>The cluster is focused on the green transformation, while representing the interests of its members and stimulating the innovation process among them.</p> <p>The cluster is a one-stop shop for green innovation and solutions.</p> <p>The cluster develops projects for application under European funds and programs of the Bulgarian government to provide funding for development activities.</p>
Bioeconomy governance model description	<p>GREEN SYNERGY cluster is established in 2011. as a non-profit organization.</p> <p>The cluster brings together and coordinates the knowledge and experience of companies, research entities and public authorities with an interest in the green transition.</p> <p>The cluster is focused on the green transformation, while representing the interests of its members and stimulating the innovation process among them.</p> <p>The cluster is a one-stop shop for green innovation and solutions.</p> <p>The cluster develops projects for application under European funds and programs of the Bulgarian government to provide funding for development activities.</p> <p>The cluster mission is to support SMEs and public authorities in delivering green innovations and green growth.</p> <p>Main objectives are to:</p> <p>Promote, identify and realize different energy efficiency, RES and R&D projects in the sustainable energy field, thus contributing to the EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL.</p> <p>Promote and develop natural resource efficiency concepts among cluster members & circular economy solutions</p> <p>take an active part in the Green Energy Transition, so as to achieve climate neutral Europe in 2050.</p> <p>Position the cluster as an innovative brand for green energy solutions and services.</p> <p>Take part in the transition towards sustainable energy intensify cluster and business network collaboration</p> <p>inspire new ideas among cluster members and establish more</p>

	<p>competitive environment among them. Internationalize cluster members; and establish partnerships with other clusters and organisations at international level.</p>
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	“Support for the sustainable development of Green Synergy Cluster” and is implemented with the financial support of OPIC 2014-2020, co-financed by the EU through the ERDF.
Model's sectors and value chains	<p>Sectoral industries. Professional, scientific and technical activities: M72 Scientific research and development. Sectoral Industries (NACE 4 digit). Architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis: M7112 Engineering activities and related technical consultancy. Cross-sectoral industries. Environmental Industries. Industrial Alliances and Ecosystems. Ecosystems: Renewable Energy. Technology fields. F\ : Mechanical engineering; lighting; heating; weapons; blasting: Heat exchange in general. S3 EU priority areas. Sustainable innovation: Climate change - Sustainable innovation: Resource efficiency - Sustainable innovation: Sustainable energy & renewables.</p>
Sector of governance model	<p>Green Synergy is a cluster organisation implementing sustainable solutions in the following fields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable Energy Planning. • Renewable Energy. • Energy Efficiency. • Renewable Energy Communities. • Smart Cities and Positive Energy Districts. • Biomass to energy. • Bio-based industries.
Societal objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy communities and consumer (co-)ownership in renewable energy Co-operative societies intended to primarily benefit their members. • Capacity-building programmes. • Energy education.
Environmental objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smarter buildings for better energy performance. • Monitoring of energy demand. • Demand response in energy-efficient residential buildings. • Providing energy efficiency, flexibility, generation and storage services, based on user preferences and requests. • Supporting setting up financial and non-financial support schemes for energy efficiency and/or small-scale renewable energy investments. • Development of innovative schemes for energy efficiency/RES. • Energy performance assessment and certification of buildings. • Working with buildings related databases.
Economic objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing authorities to deliver new policies. • Enhancing authorities to deliver energy efficiency measures. • Support public authorities in the development of policy scenarios and transition roadmaps. • Engagement of policymakers in the energy transition. • Establishment of sustainable and competitive bio-based industry. • Involvement of primary sectors as strategic partners in bio-based value

	<p>chains.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stimulation investment & creation of new, local value chains.
Resources to be used	Green Synergy Cluster accelerates green innovation for a green transition by promoting innovation capacity and cooperation between stakeholders.
Driving forces of model/strategy	<p>Mission:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting business for green growth by providing innovative energy services. <p>Vision:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To become a leading Bulgarian cluster for implementation of innovative eco energy solutions. <p>Goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for national and local initiatives in the field of green innovation and cluster cooperation. • Strengthening the capacity of cluster members. • Internationalization.
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	<p>Energy Agency of Plovdiv</p> <p>Install Engineering</p> <p>Enercon</p> <p>Oberon Konzeptbau</p> <p>Crane</p> <p>Heliodom</p> <p>Solery</p> <p>Stenli Frigo</p> <p>Sofena Ltd.</p> <p>ISE Energy</p> <p>Schneider Electric</p> <p>Ellon Ltd</p>
Decision-making and voting mechanism	N/A
Dispute resolution processes	N/A
Synergies with other regions and governance models	<p>International cooperation.</p> <p>Targeted countries:</p> <p>Brazil</p> <p>Mexico</p> <p>Philippines</p> <p>Transnational cooperation.</p> <p>Targeted countries:</p> <p>Denmark</p> <p>France</p> <p>Germany</p>

	<p>Spain Italy</p> <p>Transnational support activities: Participation at missions/events/study visits/fairs - Support to collaborative activities/etc.</p> <p>Further information: Green Synergy cluster is investigating possibilities for participation in matchmaking missions in third countries, appropriate for current cluster members.</p> <p>International support activities: Support to collaborative activities/etc.</p> <p>Further information: Participation at the Low carbon business mission in Mexico, setting up an Internationalisation Strategy Plan, signing NATUREEF MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING for establishment of European Strategic Cluster Partnership, focused on the Natural Resource Efficiency - participation in a study visit at the Innovation Network for Biomass (INBIOM) in Denmark.</p>
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	<p>TRACE-KEI</p> <p>Bulgarian Employers Association Innovative Technologies</p>
Circular economy and development	<p>Circular Economy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Circular Cities and Regions Initiatives. •Clean environment and zero pollution.
Support measures/tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •News, trends, and information on support programmes. •Information on funding sources and technology providers. •Project applications, coordination and management of projects. •Access to knowledge on the best available technologies and business models. •Capacity-building and training workshops. •Improved management of energy and resources. •Development of innovative ideas and technologies. •Fact finding missions in EU and third countries. •Technology transfer activities. •Facilitation of partnership agreements. •Help building a green image which helps target new customer markets.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	N/A
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	<p>Providing access to new contacts and business opportunities.</p> <p>Development of analysis of the new incoming Technologies and innovative products.</p> <p>Development of ideas for innovative projects.</p> <p>Development of ideas for joint projects.</p> <p>Encouraging innovation among cluster members.</p> <p>Searching for suitable project partners for project implementations .</p> <p>Participation in study visits .</p>

	<p>Sending regular information for available Business events and business missions.</p> <p>Sending regular information for available national funding opportunities.</p> <p>Participation in regional energy conferences and fairs.</p> <p>Organisation of c2c & b2b events with other parties.</p> <p>Organisation of regular GSC meetings.</p> <p>Facilitation of collaboration between members.</p> <p>Facilitation of regular exchange of information and experience.</p> <p>Different promotional activities, e.g. economic regional yearbooks, press releases, promotional fair materials, etc.</p>
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	N/A
Relevant sources	https://web.gea.uni-sofia.bg/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/ETGG SME 2030 Report Final Version 2.pdf

5.2 Case 2: Resilient Thessaloniki

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Resilient Thessaloniki
Organization name	City of Thessaloniki
Website	https://thessaloniki.gr/%CE%B8%CE%AD%CE%BB%CF%89-%CE%B1%CF%80%CF%8C-%CF%84%CE%BF%CE%BD-%CE%B4%CE%AE%CE%BC%CE%BF/%CE%B8%CE%AD%CE%BB%CF%89-%CE%BD%CE%B1-%CE%B5%CE%BE%CF%85%CF%80%CE%B7%CF%81%CE%B5%CF%84%CE%B7%CE%B8%CF%8E/resilient/
Region/Geographical scale	Greece / Thessaloniki
Year	2015-2019
Stage of implementation	Completed
Executive Summary	The Resilience Strategy is based on eight city values (Social Cohesion, Local Identity & Heritage, Environmental Management, Health & Well-being, Youth Empowerment, Multi-stakeholder Engagement, Technology Adaptation, Economic Prosperity), which represent the city's identity and guide how future will be planned.
Bioeconomy governance model description	Reframe waste management: Waste management is currently dealt with at a national, regional, and local (municipal) scale with little participation from citizens and local entrepreneurs. The aim is to embed circular economy principles to make waste a resource for new products and services, to reduce the amount of waste the city generates, to promote recycling and upcycling, improve recycling rates, cultivate environmental awareness, and create new local economic opportunities. The Local Waste Management Action Plan commits the city to recycle 60% of its total waste by 2020. Improving waste collection, increasing recycling and up cycling streams are the first steps towards establishing a more circular economy. With the support of policies such as Green Public Procurement, we will implement circular economy practices in the city. These will influence consumption patterns , encourage re-use and repair, establish Green Spots and seminars and activities for up-cycling. We will also explore the development of urban composting systems. Strengthening our circular economy will help us tackle climate change, create employment opportunities and boost economic growth.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Urban
Statutory level	Thessaloniki was selected in 2014 as part of the second cohort of cities to join the 100 Resilient Cities (100RC) network. We consider this a unique opportunity to implement a robust, participatory approach and create a long-term strategy to address current and future challenges, and in doing so to connect with other cities and

	<p>organizations across the world via the 100RC network. The 100RC methodology provided an innovative model for the local authority to develop a holistic city strategy in collaboration with adjacent municipalities, local academic institutions, the non-profit sector, private stakeholders, citizens, and communities of the city. More than 40 organizations and 2000 citizens participated in our resilience dialogue, ensuring the strategy aligns with and complements other strategic initiatives in the local, regional, national and international domain, including the city's 5 year Operational Plan 2020 and European Strategy for 2020. The Resilience Strategy reflects our ambitions as a city. We want to be inclusive; locally oriented but with international partnerships and exchanges; and forward looking to address interrelated challenges, goals, targets and actions.</p>
Model's sectors and value chains	N/A
Sector of governance model	No Specific Sector
Societal objectives	Food security, Sustainability, Climate change, Employment and economic development, Dependence on non-renewables
Environmental objectives	Food security, Sustainability, Climate change, Employment and economic development, Dependence on non-renewables
Economic objectives	<p>Urban economy policy agenda The three foundational components of the urban economy are employment, productivity, and urban finance. These are interlinked and influence one other. However, there is limited understanding or assessment of these linkages in Thessaloniki. Understanding the detailed composition of the economic structure of the metropolitan area is a necessary first step to deciding how to improve the productivity of individual sectors, firms, and the city's economy as a whole. This policy agenda will focus on the productivity of the urban economy and its distributional consequences for poverty and inequality, while understanding which "local" characteristics of the city can have wider spatial and macro-economic effects. This will help develop effective and long-term strategies to support priority sectors and economic clusters, diversify the economy and prepare it for future global economic shocks, develop economic and employment opportunities, and support cross-sector collaboration and shared learning. Objective B: Local cluster economic activities Thessaloniki's traditional economy included a mix of activities including a food market, flower market, jewellery district and so on. In recent years, these clusters either disappeared due to changes in the economic structure of the city or transformed into new areas of economic development, mostly related to leisure and services. New activities in the creative industries sector have now also appeared, which have helped to rejuvenate these areas of the city. To support these industries, the city must identify new</p>

	<p>spatial arrangements and seek solutions to protect, enable and promote these clusters (both existing and emerging) based on new governance and urban planning models (e.g. the Business Improvement District model). In addition to the spatial clustering of economic activities on a micro-scale, there are clusters at the macro- scale. In the national economy, the metropolitan area of Thessaloniki is recognized as a hub for creative activities and networks, including graphic and industrial design, and even music. We will create a toolbox of policies to strengthen these economic clusters. We will also pilot alternative solutions and models to enhance productivity, develop effective and long-term strategies to support priority sectors and economic clusters, enhance productivity and develop new economic and employment opportunities, facilitate new partnership opportunities, and strengthen multi-stakeholder collaboration.</p>
Resources to be used	N/A
Driving forces of model/strategy	<p>A. Urban economy policy agenda B. Local cluster economic activities C. New cross-sector partnerships D. Metropolitan collaboration E. Performance-based management F. Financial resilience G. Municipal capital investment plan H. Local risk reduction and risk management systems I. Informed citizens and decision makers Thessaloniki's Goals, Objectives and Actions</p>
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	Municipality of Thessaloniki, Community Groups and Social Business
Decision-making and voting mechanism	N/A
Dispute resolution processes	N/A
Synergies with other regions and governance models	<p>Thessaloniki is part of the URBACT Resilient Europe network that applies innovative governance methodologies to assess what city resilience means for each city and help them formulate Integrated Action Plans.</p> <p>Thessaloniki is focusing on promoting cycling, developing cycling culture amongst younger citizens, and providing new cycling infrastructure.</p> <p>The neighbourhood of Toumpa (in the 4th Borough) was selected as an Urban Living Lab in which a local Action Plan will be developed. The Action Plan includes installing bike lanes and stands across the city, upgrading city lighting, and rolling out awareness campaigns in local schools.</p> <p>Changing attitudes towards cycling is an important element of the program. We have great weather for cycling, but we need to get people thinking about it as a mode of transport and not just a recreational activity.</p> <p>We are also looking into best practice around the design of</p>

	<p>the cycle network to make sure it connects the city centre with the adjacent municipalities of the metropolitan area. We are also considering bike sharing schemes and innovative funding mechanisms to deliver the program. The program is due to complete in 2018. To help deliver it, we joined the URBACT Local Support Group which brings together stakeholders from the local council, public transport authority, private firms, civil society groups, and the cycling community.</p>
<p>Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region</p>	<p>New cross-sector partnerships The needs of our communities and citizens are changing rapidly. To improve the quality and delivery of city services, we will work with stakeholders from the private, academic and civil society sectors to form new partnerships that make the most effective use of limited resources, create positive impacts and unlock creativity and innovation in the areas of education, urban development, technology, energy, climate adaptation, health and more. We have already developed strong and productive partnerships relating to the co-design and delivery of new social and cultural services. We will build on these successes to further develop new cross-sector partnership opportunities, strengthen multi-stakeholder collaboration, strengthen social cohesion and build community resilience, develop new economic and employment opportunities, and promote co-creation of city strategies and services. Partnerships Model Approach Triple-Helix or Quadruple-Helix Stakeholders: public, private (industry/corporate), academia, society. There are two ways to structure this model: 1) Society is treated as the recipient of a service, and the design and development responsibilities lie with experts in the triple helix (public, private, academic sectors); 2) Civil society actors are part of the scheme development process. They actively engage by expressing what their needs are and brainstorming ideas. In certain cases, they may even voluntarily provide data and information to help other partners in the quadruple-helix to understand citizens' behaviours and needs. Pay-for-Success/ Social Impact Bonds/ Human Capital Performance Bonds Stakeholders: government, private funders (investment banks etc). Social Impact bonds, also known as pay-for-success financing, are performance contracts between the government and private funders (e.g. investment banks). In projects financed by social impact bonds, the private sector is responsible for financing and implementing a social service (e.g. school, community development, correctional facility, etc.) and will only receive repayments by the government if prescribed, quantified performance metrics are met. In order to stay objective and impartial, a third-party independent appraiser will monitor and report how well the private sector has achieved the performance metrics. Collective Impact Initiatives.</p>

	<p>Stakeholders: Funders (philanthropic and other), non-profits, civil society and community organizations, private sector, academia.</p> <p>Collective Impact is a new approach to adaptive problem-solving. This includes the commitment of a group of actors from different sectors to a common agenda and specific problem, using common indicators and data to track progress.</p> <p>Social Development Partnerships Stakeholders: Local authorities, civil society / social economy.</p> <p>This is a new partnership model for local governments and civil society that started in Greece in 2016. In it, municipalities identify services to outsource (social services, management of parks, public spaces and cultural institutions, sanitation, etc), and establish partnerships to source these services from social cooperatives or social-benefit enterprises.</p> <p>3. C.02 MULTILEVEL GOVERNANCE 100 100 Resilient Cities Thessaloniki Resilience Strategy</p>
Circular economy and development	N/A
Support measures/tools	Implement awareness-raising campaigns to increase societal participation
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	N/A
Transition process	Bottom up
Monitoring	<p>Developing the strategy is the first step on our journey towards a more resilient future. The next steps are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue the resilience dialogue both inside the city and with external stakeholders and communities through seminars, workshops, and open discussions; • Secure additional resources (national and international) and develop partnerships with the 100RC Platform partners; • Develop a yearly action and investment plan along with a Monitoring and Evaluation Report. <p>To guide and promote the implementation of the Resilience Strategy, the city and its partners will monitor progress through local and global indicators and data sets, outlined in the table below.</p> <p>The challenge that arises from the use of the above indicators is the availability of the specific data sets in order to have a measurable evaluation.</p> <p>This is why the Resilience Strategy includes a set of Actions that will improve the way data is aggregated, managed and shared to facilitate the monitoring of the strategy by all relevant stakeholders.</p>

Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	N/A
Relevant sources	N/A

5.3 Case 3: Circular Bio-based Delta

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Circular Bio-based Delta (Triple Helix Network with the political back-up of 3 regional governments)
Organization name	Circular Bio-based Delta
Website	https://circularbiobaseddelta.nl/ https://biconsortium.eu/node/316
Region/Geographical scale	Netherlands / Multi-regional
Year	2012
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The Bio-based Delta is a triple helix structured organisation for Southwest Netherlands. SMEs, large industries, knowledge institutes and governments work together to become a leading region in the bio-based economy. Various initiatives are being fostered, amongst others Bio Innovation Garden (Zeeland), Green Chemistry Campus (Bergen op Zoom) and Nieuw Prinsenland (Dinteloord).
Bioeconomy governance model description	Public-private partnership, including a triple helix approach and based on membership. Together with the members the organisation aims at facilitating collaborations between the business community, provinces, water boards, municipalities and knowledge and educational institutions in the region of Southwest Netherland. The Delta is the network and the service provider that makes knowledge and innovation accessible. The Delta is backed-up by 3 regions: North Brabant, Zeeland, and South Holland.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	No, but 3 regions are backing-up the initiative (North Brabant, Zeeland, and South Holland) at the institutional level.
Model's sectors and value chains	Green Feedstock, Green Building Blocks and Sustainable process industries.
Sector of governance model	Chemical industry, chemical recycling, agriculture.
Societal objectives	Climate neutrality.
Environmental objectives	Climate change and environment.
Economic objectives	Sustainability, technological innovation.
Resources to be used	Land, water, waste/by-products.
Driving forces of model/strategy	Climate change and environment.

Type of strategy	Mixed
Key actors	Regional administration, RTD organisations, Companies and SMEs.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	<i>Information not available</i>
Dispute resolution processes	<i>Information not available</i>
Synergies with other regions and governance models	3 regions from the southwest Netherlands are teaming-up.
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Policies on circular bioeconomy and circular economy in Zeeland.
Circular economy and development	National Circular Economy strategy. The programme is implemented since 2015 with an update in 2020.
Support measures/tools	Through the participation in the Bioeconomy Pilot of the Vanguard initiative, 7 demo cases with a transregional value chain approach are under development. Other initiatives are ongoing as listed below: -Shared Research Center Biorizon, an initiative of TNO, VITO, ECN and Green Chemistry Campus. -Redefinery is to realize large-scale refining of lignocellulose into sugars, lignin and energy. The aim is to start up the biorefinery in 2021-2022. -The aim of the Sugar Delta project is to enable a bio-refinery plant in the southwest of the Netherlands, where value is added to sugar or starch by converting them into chemical products and ingredients.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	Land use change
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	<i>Information not available</i>
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	Natural & geographical (expected), since some of the 3 regions are coastal and more vulnerable to climate change.
Relevant sources	https://www.zeeland.nl/economie/circular-biobased-economy

5.4 Case 4: Regional Innovation Strategy Sachsen-Anhalt 2014 – 2020

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Regional Innovation Strategy Sachsen-Anhalt 2014 – 2020
Organization name	Ministry for Science and Economy

Website	https://mw.sachsen-anhalt.de/fileadmin/Bibliothek/Politik_und_Verwaltung/MW/Publikationen/RIS/Regionale_Innovationsstrategie_2014-2020_final.pdf
Region/Geographical scale	Germany / Region
Year	2014
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	"Chemistry and Bioeconomy" is one of the five identified lead markets of the strategy. The state government is pursuing a broad approach, including the broadening of the raw material base by opening the use of domestic lignite and the material and energetic use of non-edible renewable raw materials such as wood.
Bioeconomy governance model description	The governance of the strategy is quite linked to the action of the regional bioeconomy cluster. Through the founding of this cluster in 2012, the bioeconomy approach of the strategy focuses on lignocellulose-based bioeconomy, as well as the coupled and cascade use of wood and woody by-products. The cluster has assured funding till 2026.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	Yes
Model's sectors and value chains	Bioenergy, biomaterials, biotechnology
Sector of governance model	Agriculture, chemical industry, plastic manufacturing
Societal objectives	Dependence on non-renewables. As former region of the German Democratic Republic, an important energy share still come from carbon-based power plants; that may cause issues related to the so-called Just Transition.
Environmental objectives	Climate change and environment
Economic objectives	Sustainability, dependence on non-renewables
Resources to be used	Land, by-products, waste, labour
Driving forces of model/strategy	Climate change and environment, technological innovation
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	Bioeconomy cluster, public administration, Academia, companies & SMEs
Decision-making and voting mechanism	<i>Information not available</i>
Dispute resolution processes	<i>Information not available</i>
Synergies with other regions and governance models	Saxony
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Energiewende ("Energy Turnaround") in Germany since 2011, Strukturwandel in Germany ("Structure Turnaround") for coal-intensive regions, Hydrogen Strategy for Saxony-Anhalt.

Circular economy and development	One of the leading projects mentioned in the strategy is a kind of Demonstration centre for Circular and Resource efficient economy, that includes plans for the valorisation of the bio-waste. It is not known if this centre has been built. Moreover, since October 2020 the Law for Circular Economy applies national wide and the "Länder" should apply measures for its implementation. Due to the weight of the chemical industry in the region, measures related to the circular and resource efficient economy of the so-called "chemie parks" are observed in the regional innovation strategy.
Support measures/tools	Richtlinie "Sachsen-Anhalt Revier 2038": it will include measures related to use of hydrogen as source of energy (July 2022; in preparation). This measure is addressed as part of the "Structure Turnaround" and initially addressed for municipalities and counties / Strategic international research collaborations: The regional bioeconomy cluster co-organises yearly an International Bioeconomy Conference (10th edition in 2022).
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	Social Equity due to the "Structure Turnaround", particularly while transitioning from carbon-based to renewable energy.
Transition process	Bottom up
Monitoring	<i>Information not available</i>
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	Social, economic, "Structure Turnaround"
Relevant sources	The expected update of this strategy (2021-2027) could not be found.

5.5 Case 5: BioökonomieREVIER

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	BioökonomieREVIER
Organization name	Federal Ministry for Science, Research and Education + diverse academic/industrial partners from North-Rhine-Westphalia
Website	https://www.biooekonomierevier.de
Region/Geographical scale	Germany / Regional
Year	2020
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The Rhenisch Revier is the first model region for sustainable bioeconomy funded in Germany. Co-ordinated by Forschungszentrum Jülich, it strives at bringing different people together for the bioeconomy in the region. It encompasses the QH approach with a close work with municipalities, civic organizations, and companies in order to scale up bio-based innovations.
Bioeconomy governance model description	A model region for the circular bioeconomy: The holistic approach of the Rhenisch Revier should inspire other

	regions in Germany to step up towards the bioeconomy approach.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	YES. Funded by the Federal Ministry but with the commitment of the regional government of North-Rhine Westphalia; public-private partnership.
Model's sectors and value chains	Bioenergy, biomaterials, biotechnology, food & feed
Sector of governance model	Agriculture, food, paper, chemicals, plastics, textile industry
Societal objectives	Dependence on non-renewables due to the traditional mining history in the region. In first semester 2022, around 95% from energy production came from coal (mostly) and gas. That may cause issues related to the so-called Just Transition.
Environmental objectives	Climate change and environment
Economic objectives	Sustainability, dependence on non-renewables
Resources to be used	Land, by-products, waste, labour
Driving forces of model/strategy	Climate change and environment, technological innovation
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	RTD organisations, regional government, municipalities, federal government, companies & SMEs.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	<i>Information not available</i>
Dispute resolution processes	<i>Information not available</i>
Synergies with other regions and governance models	<i>not known</i>
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Energiewende ("Energy Turnaround") in Germany since 2011, Strukturwandel in Germany ("Structure Turnaround") for coal-intensive regions; Since July 2021 there is a regional law on climate protection in order to be GHG neutral till 2045; Circular Economy Law since Feb. 2022.
Circular economy and development	The model region is intended at sustainable bioeconomy, so it is assumed that circular economy principles are followed; the recent Circular Economy Law focuses particularly on the raw materials (mining) and building sector.
Support measures/tools	In March 2022 it was announced 72 M € coming from the regional government to support the model region; at the end of 2021 it was announced 6.3 M € funding for a start-up village related with bioeconomy in Jülich; The Coordination Office of the Rhenisch Revier is organising awareness raising activities for the civil actors in the region. e.g., for students (Innovation Award) and commissioning a study on the regional education and qualification strategies in regards to the bioeconomy. 160 M € will fund 24

	innovative climate protection projects in around 90 municipalities according the "Kommunaler Klimaschutz. NRW" programme (using EFRD).
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	Social Equity due to the "Structure Turnaround", particularly while transitioning from carbon-based to renewable energy.
Transition process	Bottom up
Monitoring	<i>Information not available, but probably monitoring tools are in nascent stage.</i>
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	Social, economic, "Structure Turnaround"
Relevant sources	N/A

5.6 Case 6: Bavaria's Bioeconomy Strategy

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Bavaria's Bioeconomy Strategy
Organization name	Bavarian State Ministry for Economic Affairs, Regional Development and Energy (Leading Ministry)
Website	https://www.biooekonomiestrategie.bayern/startseite
Region/Geographical scale	Germany / Region
Year	2020
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	It is a strongly implementation-oriented strategy. It was an outcome of a extend participatory process involving 300 experts from different disciplines (consulted through digital workshops and interviews). From 10 chapters of the strategy, 5 are addressing society, administration and politics, agriculture and forestry, companies, science, and research. There is a specific focus on society and awareness raising. It includes 50 measures.
Bioeconomy governance model description	The Bavarian Bioeconomy Strategy was developed under the leadership of the Bavarian State Ministry for Economic Affairs, Regional Development and Energy and closely accompanied by the Bavarian Bioeconomy Expert Council (Sachverständigenrat Bioökonomie Bayern, existing since 2015) and the Interministerial Working Group on Renewable Resources and Bioeconomy. It involved a participatory process with 300 experts.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	Yes, the strategy belongs to the policies driven by the Ministry for Economic Affairs, involving also other Ministries though an Interministerial Working Group

Model's sectors and value chains	Bioenergy, biomaterials, food & feed, sustainable use of biomass.
Sector of governance model	Agriculture (straw, fiber, oil seeds), forestry, industrial sector, Bio-waste
Societal objectives	Climate change
Environmental objectives	Climate change, biodiversity
Economic objectives	Sustainability, resource efficiency
Resources to be used	Land, waste, by-products
Driving forces of model/strategy	Technological innovation, Climate change and environment
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	Bioeconomy Expert Council, academia, companies, SMEs, Ministries involved in the Interministerial Working Group on Renewable Resources and Bioeconomy. Officially there is a network of actors composed of Cluster Offensive Bayern, Bayerische Forschungs- und Innovationsagentur, Bayerische Forschungsallianz, Bayern Innovativ, C.A.R.M.E.N, and Technologie- und Förderzentrum.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	<i>Information not available</i>
Dispute resolution processes	<i>Information not available</i>
Synergies with other regions and governance models	Not defined, but several measures for strengthen cooperation are foreseen e.g., digital platform on bioeconomy, international stakeholder conference, support cross-regional networks
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Policies on research and innovation, technology transfer and climate. By 2030 the emissions of CO ₂ should be reduced to 65%.
Circular economy and development	Two chapters address the circular economy and strengthening cooperation within its framework.
Support measures/tools	Different initiatives have been initiated since the publication of the strategy e.g., the FORUM 3B facilitates partnerships between bioeconomy-related actors since 2022; Online-Forum Biopolymere 2022; "BayBioökonomie-Scale-Up": this is a funding programme addressed to innovative polymers based on sustainable raw materials, with deadlines in April and June 2022; VentureCon Bioeconomy in 2022 dedicated to start-ups; "International Sustainable Economy Forum" in 2022.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	Land use change
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	The implementation is monitored by the Bioeconomy Expert Council, but the timings and methodology are not set in the strategy.

Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	Not known, but the strategy has a particular focus on society and awareness raising for the understanding of what bioeconomy means.
Relevant sources	https://biooekonomierat-bayern.de/ https://forum-3b.de/

5.7 Case 7: Alliance Plant³

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Alliance Plant ³
Organization name	University of Greifswald / Ministry of Science, Culture, National and European affairs of Mecklenburg-Pomerania
Website	https://biooekonomie.uni-greifswald.de/
Region/Geographical scale	Germany / Region
Year	2019
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The Alliance Plant ³ aims at making a substantial contribution to an innovation-based structural change in the north-eastern Mecklenburg- Pomerania region. It is an open innovation network, and it acts as think tank for new ideas and academic support of value chains based on bioeconomy. The initiative should be seen as model for sustainable transformation of the rural areas since this region is mainly agricultural and coastal.
Bioeconomy governance model description	This is an alliance to support the research and development on bioeconomy, as well as the "Structure Turnaround" in this former region of the German Democratic Republic. It was initiated by a public-private partnership composed of a university, the regional investment agency, and a company. It is funded by the German national programme WIR. It has regional focus in Pomerania. It is supported by an Advisory Council, so the work of the Alliance is aligned with the regional strategy and funding priorities of the programme WIR! It has a Steering Group that monitors the calls and evaluate the proposals.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	No
Model's sectors and value chains	Bioenergy, Biomaterials, Food & Feed
Sector of governance model	Agriculture, livestock, blue economy
Societal objectives	"Structure turnaround" related to some less-developed German regions.
Environmental objectives	Climate change.
Economic objectives	Employment and economic development.

Resources to be used	Land, water
Driving forces of model/strategy	Demographics, Climate change and environment
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	Academia, companies & SMEs, regional development agencies, regional and national administration.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	<i>Information not available</i>
Dispute resolution processes	<i>Information not available</i>
Synergies with other regions and governance models	Pomerania belongs to the German "Land" of Mecklenburg-Pomerania. Although the alliance is focused in the north-east part of this "Land", a potential cross-fertilisation with Mecklenburg is intrinsically expected.
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	"Structure Turnaround"; "Düngelandesverordnung" (related to policies to control nitrate leakage in agriculture) expected for November 2022.
Circular economy and development	German Law on circular economy since 2012 and transposition of the European Directive on waste (2018) in 2020.
Support measures/tools	Within the funding programme WIR!, funded by the Federal Ministry of Science and Education, some calls to support research and innovation on the bioeconomy are published.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	"Structure Turnaround", conflicts with farmers related to the "Düngelandesverordnung" in preparation.
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	Though the Advisory Council the actions implemented and funded through the Alliance are monitored in order they are aligned with the priorities of the funding programme WIR! and the policies of Meklenburg-Pomerania on this regard.
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	Geographical, social
Relevant sources	https://www.innovation-strukturwandel.de/strukturwandel/de/innovation-strukturwandel/wir/wir.html

5.8 Case 8: Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy

Organization name	Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development (Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua y Desarrollo Rural)
Website	https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agriculturapescaaquaydesarrollorural/areas/politica-agraria-comun/desarrollo-rural/paginas/estrategia-andaluza-bioeconomia.html
Region/Geographical scale	Andalusia/Spain
Year	2018
Stage of implementation	In progress. Some measures implemented
Executive Summary	Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy (ACBS) contributes to the sustainable growth and competitiveness of the region. The focus of the ACBS is the development of activities among three segments of the bioeconomy value chain: the production of biomass, the technical processing, and the consumer markets.
Bioeconomy governance model description	<p>The model is focused on the construction of a diversified and sustainable region in which the bioeconomy represents a crucial factor of development aligned with human welfare, social equity, adaptation to climate change and lower dependence on external resources. It involves all actors of the quadruple helix: knowledge centres, administrations, companies, and citizens.</p> <p>The governance of the Strategy is based on the participation and cooperation of both public and private actors. The Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development oversees coordinating the Strategy and driving the governance process until its final approval. This strategy was elaborated with the cooperation of other Regional Ministries and experts in the field.</p> <p>The general objective is to contribute to the sustainable growth and development of Andalusia by boosting actions aimed at the promotion of the production of biological renewable resources and processes.</p> <p>The general and strategic objectives will be achieved through a set of measures structured around four vertical strategic lines: Resources, Infrastructures and Logistics, Processing and Markets development, and through four cross-cutting programmes.</p>
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	Yes
Model's sectors and value chains	<p>Agri-food value chain: Sustainable production and availability of biomass resources. Industrial Biomass processing processes and bioproducts and bioenergy industrial production (biorefineries, bioindustries, integrated biorefineries).</p> <p>Market development for bioproducts and bioenergy</p>
Sector of governance model	Agriculture, Fisheries, Livestock, Forestry and Silviculture, Agri-food, Chemical industry, Biotechnology, etc
Societal objectives	<p>Increasing of consumption of bioproducts and bioenergy.</p> <p>Promoting gender equality.</p> <p>Incorporation of youngsters in the areas of the circular bioeconomy.</p>

Environmental objectives	<p>Improving the sustainability and competitiveness of the agri-food, fishing and forestry sectors by promoting the use of innovative practices that will favour and develop a circular economy.</p> <p>Promoting the reuse of resources, water, gases, nutrients and the recovery of waste and plant debris in order to obtain other products, uses or energies.</p> <p>Increasing the availability of sustainable biomass for its use in innovative treatments.</p> <p>Increasing the volume of bioindustries and biorefineries in Andalusia.</p>
Economic objectives	<p>Stimulating the competitiveness of those industries working with biological resources by promoting innovation, the generation of knowledge and technology transfer.</p> <p>Favouring research, innovation, and qualification in relation to bioeconomy.</p> <p>Reinforcing inter-administrative coordination and the synergies with other schemes and work programmes of different areas.</p> <p>Increasing the bioproducts and bioenergy markets and consumption in Andalusia.</p>
Resources to be used	Biomass resources, Water, Waste/By-products.
Driving forces of model/strategy	<p>The model drives through four strategic lines:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sustainable production and availability of biomass resources. 2. Infrastructures and logistics Management. 3. Industrial processing processes and bioproducts and bioenergy industrial production capacity. 4. Market development for bioproducts and bioenergy. <p>Besides, there are four transversal programmes to impulse these strategic lines.</p>
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	<p>Andalusian Cluster of Circular Bioeconomy: it will favour the generation of knowledge, the real transfer of innovation and the effective visibility of the progresses made by the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia, through the collaboration between actors.</p> <p>Circular Bioeconomy Observatory: it will provide an instrument to support the Andalusian circular bioeconomy from the points of view of the Public Administration and expert people of the private sector. Its main objectives will be to stimulate the circular bioeconomy, promote its development and monitor its evolution.</p>
Decision-making and voting mechanism	The Monitoring Committee will periodically evaluate the degree of compliance with the strategic lines and measures of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy through the monitoring and control of a series of indicators.
Dispute resolution processes	The Interdepartmental Commission aims to establish a clear context to support the circular bioeconomy with the collaboration of all the agents and/or institutional actors. To do this, the coordination between Regional Governments and other administrative centres is required. This coordination will be achieved through tools and instruments

	that will allow resolution of conflicts (regular meetings, work groups, ...).
Synergies with other regions and governance models	European Bioeconomy Strategy, Spanish Bioeconomy Strategy, Green Deal, 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Andalusian Circular Economy Law, Strategic Plan to improve the competitiveness of the agricultural, livestock, fisheries and agro-industrial sector and the rural development in Andalusia.
Circular economy and development	<p>Connecting the bioeconomy and the circular economy, integrating the one into the other is crucial as together they are empowered and are stronger in achieving social, economic and environmental goals than separately. Achieving a circular economic model in which the full value of (sustainably sourced) biomass resources is harnessed is the path to economic growth, sustainable resources (sustainably sourced) is path to economic growth, job creation and environmental sustainability.</p> <p>There is a draft Andalusian circular economy law that will integrate aspects of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy.</p> <p>environmental objectives than separately.</p> <p>The compatibility of approaches between the two is manifest, and both can benefit from synergies and seize the same opportunities.</p>
Support measures/tools	<p>Communication and awareness-raising on the circular bioeconomy.</p> <p>Promotion R&D+I+T for the development and expansion of the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia: the creation of a catalogue of good practices and portfolio of successful projects, technological innovations and business ideas, tools to favour the technological transfer, actives and services to promote the transfer of knowledge, stimulating the creation of a Focus Group, the introduction of the circular bioeconomy in training programmes.</p> <p>Implementing economic resources to promote the access the Circular Bioeconomy aims into the private sector.</p> <p>Funding access to facilitate the development of the circular bioeconomy: financial instruments available, foreign investment.</p> <p>Promotion the cooperation, coordination, and monitoring: cluster, observatory, clarifying the regulatory and legal framework, Interdepartmental Commission to promote and monitor the circular bioeconomy, Monitoring Committee, Technical Office, the panel of specific indicators.</p>
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	<p>Limited knowledge on the characteristics of a great variety of biomass resources.</p> <p>Deficient management of the by-products.</p> <p>Insufficient management of forest resources.</p> <p>Seasonal variation of biomass resources.</p> <p>Little development of the integrated biorefineries and bio-based industries.</p> <p>Lack of clear and recognized regulations of the products of biological origin</p> <p>Unawareness of what the circular bioeconomy is and what it represents by great part of society.</p>

	<p>Lack of innovative business culture to face the technological adaptation.</p> <p>Little development of integrated biorefineries and bio-based industries derived from livestock production.</p> <p>Unawareness of what the circular bioeconomy implies for certain business areas and the public sector.</p>
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	<p>Monitoring and evaluating the results of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy are complementary and necessary processes to confirm the achievement of its objectives and, if necessary, to modify the measures or their approach to achieve them.</p> <p>In this way, the following elements are proposed to implement the monitoring and evaluation of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strategy Monitoring and Evaluation Committee: it will regularly evaluate the degree of compliance with the strategic lines and measures of the Andalusian Strategy for Circular Bioeconomy through the monitoring and control of a series of indicators. The Committee will also be alert to identify the needs that may arise during the implementation and development of the Strategy. 2. Technical office of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy: it will oversee designing and implementing tools and preparing the documents that will ensure the availability of information and the reports needed for the Monitoring Committee so that it can carry out its functions. The Technical Office shall be managed by the Deputy Regional Ministry for Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development. 3. Indicator panel: these indicators are the main source of information in the Strategy's monitoring and evaluation processes, among them: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Context indicators: generated employment and turnover from the bioeconomy. Impact indicators: increase bioindustries and biorefineries, increase markets and consumption of bioproducts and bioenergy. Result indicators: linked to the strategic lines and instrumental programmes. Performance indicators: inventory of biomass resources, an impulse of sustainability practices, best available techniques. <p>The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy will be constantly updated and revised in order to take into account the achievements of the different guidelines that pave the way for a circular bioeconomy within Spain and the EU.</p>
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	<p>Great production capacity of biomass resources.</p> <p>Progressive optimization in the management of biomass resources generated by the agricultural and agri-food sectors.</p> <p>Excellent regional weather conditions for the production of biomass.</p> <p>Existence of biomass transport companies.</p>

	<p>Important agro-industrial business fabrics.</p> <p>Continuous development of bioenergy, the existence of biotechnological ecosystem, chemical cluster.</p> <p>Existence of a consolidated market for biofuels.</p> <p>Experience in Andalusia in the sustainable chemistry sector.</p> <p>Existence of logistics centres.</p>
Relevant sources	-

5.9 Case 9: Bioeconomy Strategy of Catalonia

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Bioeconomy Strategy of Catalonia
Organization name	Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda
Website	<p>https://govern.cat/govern/docs/2021/09/14/13/55/aaec0897-7a0a-42cf-ae89-454b16ca1d70.pdf</p> <p>https://ruralcat.gencat.cat/documents/20181/9479472/EBC2030_ES.pdf/27b5396b-1720-4367-af7e-be5dfca39043</p>
Region/Geographical scale	Catalonia/Spain
Year	2021
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	This strategy promotes sustainable growth and development of the Catalan economy through the promotion of the production of biological resources and local and renewable processes.
Bioeconomy governance model description	The governance model proposed in this strategy is intended to respond to four objectives that should ensure correct deployment of the strategy: 1. checking measures and actions 2. maximum coordination within the government between all departments involved in the implementation of measures and action; 3. ensuring the participation (co-governance) of all the economic and social actors and 4. Have sufficient operational capacity to execute the forecasts included in the action plans. To guarantee the correct deployment and implementation of the strategy, the strategy co-management table will be set up. The implementation is based on: triannual Action Plans, Periodic monitoring reports, a System of validation of actions and a Communication Plan. There are 7 strategic objectives (4 linked to the generation of economic activity and 3 facilitating objectives with a transversal nature) and 37 measures, in relation to: exploitation of biomass in Catalonia; development of a business network based on the circular bioeconomy throughout the territory, with special attention to the primary sector first; promotion and use of bioproducts, bioenergy and biomaterials; promotion of resilient agroforestry landscapes and the sustainable provision of ecosystem services; knowledge as a driver of the bioeconomy; strengthening the role of the Administration and adapting the regulatory and legal

	framework and preparing Catalan society for the shift towards the circular.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Rural
Statutory level	It does not have normative content. When other plans and strategies incorporate mandatory aspects, they will prevail over what is proposed by this strategy.
Model's sectors and value chains	Bioproducts, biomaterials, bioconstruction, bio-packaging, and bioenergy from biomass
Sector of governance model	Mainly the following sectors: Agriculture, Livestock, Silviculture, Aquaculture and Fisheries; forest and agricultural ecosystem services. Others included sectors are Biodegradable residues, Textile, Wood and cork, Biochemistry and Biopharmaceuticals, Food, drinks and tobacco, Paper industry, Biomass energy.
Societal objectives	Moving towards a social transformation of citizenship in favour of a more conscious and responsible, bio-based and circular development model, and that increases the wellbeing. Concretely: Positioning knowledge as the driving force behind the circular bioeconomy Strengthen the role of the Administration and adapt the regulatory and legal framework to favour the circular bioeconomy in Catalonia. Prepare Catalan society for the shift towards the circular bioeconomy.
Environmental objectives	To contribute to the protection against the effects of climate change, to the preservation of ecosystems, to the conservation of biodiversity and to the sustainable use of renewable resources. Concretely: Increase the use of forest resources by 30%. Increase by 40% the use and valorisation of co-products and by-products of the agri-food chain. Avoid the loss of agricultural land and recover the management of at least 10% of agricultural areas abandoned in the last 30 years. Reduce emissions linked to the management of livestock manure and food waste by 30%. Increase the use of renewable fuels in the primary sector by 100%. Increase organic carbon in agricultural soils in Catalonia by 0.4% annually.
Economic objectives	To open new opportunities for the economy and help protect jobs, generate investment and promote innovative supply chains for raw materials and energy, while it may also require specialised high-value-added services (biotechnology and digitalisation competence). At the same time, the circular bioeconomy has the potential to create value-added in the territory, which is essential to avoid depopulation. Concretely: Increase the weight of the bioeconomy in Catalonia's GVA by up to 5%. Increase jobs in the first sector by 10%.

	<p>Increase by 15% the incorporation of young people in the rural and maritime sectors.</p> <p>To ensure that 30% of newly created businesses in the agri-food sector are based on the circular bioeconomy.</p> <p>Increase the number of start-ups and scale-ups in the bioeconomy by 20%.</p> <p>Increase by 10% the number of companies developing technologies in the field of the bioeconomy.</p>
Resources to be used	Resources of primary sector
Driving forces of model/strategy	The seven main strategic objectives that make up the backbone of the strategy with the implementation of 37 measures. Every strategic objective has specific objectives with measures.
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	Co-management table of the strategy, chaired by the head of the Department of Climate Action, Food, and the Rural Agenda. General Secretary of Department.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	The co-management table of the strategy will monitor compliance with the strategic objectives. It will organize its tasks into thematic working groups (research and innovation, business promotion, territory, sustainability/circularity, market mechanisms, etc) or by value chains, in which the actions of all stakeholders will be proposed and analysed. The co-management table of the strategy will monitor compliance with the strategic objectives. It will organize its tasks into thematic working groups (research and innovation, business promotion, territory, sustainability/circularity, market mechanisms, etc) or by value chains, in which the actions of all stakeholders will be proposed and analysed.
Dispute resolution processes	Not defined
Synergies with other regions and governance models	European Bioeconomy Strategy, Spanish Bioeconomy Strategy, Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy, Extremadura's Green Economy, and Circular Economy Strategy.
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Strategic plans of Catalonia in relation to Agriculture, R&D, biomass energy recovery, etc
Circular economy and development	There is a Strategy to boost the green economy and the circular economy, and a Circular economy roadmap.
Support measures/tools	European Funding, Triannual Action Plans. Periodic monitoring reports. System of validation of actions Communication Plan
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	Lack of competitiveness of biomass to the international market. Outdated logistics and machinery with high CO2 emissions. Limited budget for investment and financing in infrastructure-pilot projects. Energy monopolisation of large companies. High investment by the primary by-product processing industry.

	<p>Deficit of public and private demand.</p> <p>Regulation is a barrier to generating synergies between actors or promoting projects for the generation of bioproducts.</p> <p>Dependence on European and national legislation, hinders changes in waste regulations.</p> <p>Technological dependence on other countries.</p>
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	Through 10 impact indicators: share of the bioeconomy in gross value added; jobs in the first sector, Incorporation of young people in the rural and maritime world; number of companies developing technologies in bioeconomy; exploitation of forest resources; Use and valuation of the co-products and by-products of the agri-food chain and the fishing and aquaculture sector; Recovery of the management of abandoned agricultural areas in the last 30 years; Emissions linked to the management of livestock manure and food waste; Use of fuels of renewable origin in the first sector and Soil organic carbon.
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	<p>Provision of a powerful, competitive, and innovative agricultural sector</p> <p>Availability of local biomass that can be recovered (forests, waste, industrial by-products, etc.).</p> <p>Availability of logistical structures that can complement the availability of biomass, such as the ports of Barcelona and Tarragona.</p> <p>Availability of benchmark universities and research centres with expertise in the circular bioeconomy.</p>
Relevant sources	-

5.10 Case 10: Circular Economy Strategy

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Circular Economy Strategy
Organization name	Regional Ministry of Economy and Finance
Website	https://medioambiente.jcyl.es/web/es/planificacion-indicadores-cartografia/estrategia-economia-circular-2021.html
Region/Geographical scale	Castilla y León/Spain
Year	2021
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The vision of the Circular Economy Strategy of Castilla y León is to make the Autonomous Community a competitive and innovative territory free of carbon emissions, which sustains its economy on a regenerative model, based on efficient use of natural resources, at the same time as a fair economic model that at the same time as a fair economic model that guarantees gender equality and social inclusion.

Bioeconomy governance model description	The Circular Economy Strategy of Castilla y León has been initially structured by proposing 4 strategic lines, identifying at the same time the typology of structuring actions that can be put at the service of the identified above-mentioned priorities, which are the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research and Eco-innovation. - Waste management. - Responsible consumption and new forms of economic relations - Training, awareness-raising and participation. Within the strategic line of research and eco-innovation, there is a circular bioeconomy programme coordinated by Instituto de Competitividad Empresarial.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	No
Model's sectors and value chains	Bioenergy, Bioproducts, Biomaterials
Sector of governance model	Agri-food, Automotive and components, Health and quality of life, Tourism and heritage, Energy and Industrial Environment, Habitat.
Societal objectives	Promotion of gender equality, the inclusion of the most disadvantaged sectors of society or those with difficulties in accessing the labour market.
Environmental objectives	To prioritise the overall efficiency of production processes and products, the reduction of raw material consumption, water and energy consumption and their non-toxicity.
Economic objectives	Promoting new models of economic relations based on industrial and collective cooperation. Developing new materials in the field of the bioeconomy.
Resources to be used	Water, Residues
Driving forces of model/strategy	The Circular Economy Strategy of Castilla y León will establish synergies with the Circular Bioeconomy Programme of Castilla y León to promote the recovery of waste, especially organic fractions (household waste, agricultural and food waste, pruning waste, wastewater treatment plant sludge, ashes from biomass combustion processes, etc.).
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	Working groups, social agents and stakeholders, industrial observatories, regional entities.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	In support of the Strategy, a working group will be created in which the different Regional Ministries of the Junta de Castilla y León with competences in this area, clusters and technology centres and Universities of Castilla y León will be represented, as well as the Regional Federation of Municipalities and Provinces, the social agents and other entities relevant to the circular economy, such as the Professional Associations, territorial or sectorial business associations, or consumer associations, promoting a balanced participation of men and women.
Dispute resolution processes	Not defined

Synergies with other regions and governance models	Spanish Circular Economy Strategy and Action Plans
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Circular Bioeconomy Program and Plan to boost to the agri-food bioeconomy are considered to promote economic development in bioeconomy. Bioenergy Plan.
Circular economy and development	The circular economy is developed in this strategy. In the analysis of this strategy, the aspects that are mentioned to the bioeconomy have been included and are referenced in this Excel.
Support measures/tools	Promoting Eco-Innovation, circular economy and bioeconomy forums Training and recruitment of innovation agents adapted to eco-innovation, bioeconomy, and circular economy. Funding.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	-
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	Three-year action plans, indicators system (Production and consumption indicators. waste management, secondary raw materials, greenhouse gas emissions; efficiency in the use of water) and are the following: Increase the productivity of materials by 20% (domestic consumption of materials in relation to GDP); Reduce the emission of greenhouse gases corresponding to the production sectors (industrial processes, agriculture and livestock, waste treatment and disposal) by 25% in 2030; Reduce waste generation by 15%; Increase the global rate of recycling of materials by 35%; Increase the circularity rate of materials by 40%, increasing the return of materials at the end of their useful life to the economic cycle (increase in the share of recovered materials over the total materials processed in the economy); Improve efficiency in the use of water by 10%; Ensure that at least 30% of public contracts incorporate circular economy criteria.
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	Agri-food is the macro activity with the greatest weight. 96,11 % of the surface area is rural.
Relevant sources	-

5.11 Case 11: Plan to boost to the agri-food bioeconomy

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Plan to boost to the agri-food bioeconomy
Organization name	Instituto Tecnológico Agrario de Castilla y León

Website	https://www.itacyl.es/documents/20143/0/PlanImpulsoBioeconomiaAgroalimentaria_2019.pdf/34554980-e0c5-bcca-6420-b5c8ec857cd8
Region/Geographical scale	Castilla y León/Spain
Year	2014
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The plan aims to contribute to a highly innovative, more efficient, and sustainable agri-food economy, able to reconcile the demands of productivity and competitiveness of agricultural activity.
Bioeconomy governance model description	The plan has 5 research lines and 42 work packages.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Rural
Statutory level	No
Model's sectors and value chains	By-products Bioproducts
Sector of governance model	Agriculture, Livestock, Aquaculture, Natural Resources and Food Production
Societal objectives	-
Environmental objectives	Use and valorisation of by-products/wastes from agricultural or livestock production and its industry. Efficient and sustainable water use. Development of new treatment and extraction processes to obtain sustainable bioproducts and cleaner energy.
Economic objectives	To increase the profitability of and livestock farms and related industries through sustainable and competitive production in a competitive production in an environment of climate change.
Resources to be used	Subproducts, residues, water
Driving forces of model/strategy	The plan has 5 research lines and 42 work packages. The lines are linked to: adapting efficient crop and livestock production to climate change, integrated recovery of waste and by-products, sustainable production of bioproducts and bioenergy, efficient and sustainable use of water, and ICTs and Industry 4.0.
Type of strategy	Private
Key actors	-
Decision-making and voting mechanism	Not defined
Dispute resolution processes	Not defined
Synergies with other regions and governance models	European Bioeconomy Strategy, Spanish Bioeconomy Strategy, Green Deal, 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Circular Economy Strategy of Castilla y León

Circular economy and development	This program has been an instrument for the circular economy strategy.
Support measures/tools	Own funds and European funds. Comprehensive projects. Extensive catalogue of R&D services and technical assistance to the sector. Agreements with research and technology centres. Competitive calls for funds from national programmes and European research funds. Technology transfer and specialised training programme. Incubator for innovation projects with companies in the sector. Competitive platforms.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	-
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	Through indicators of every research line.
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	Agri-food is the macro activity with the greatest weight. 96,11 % of the surface area is rural.
Relevant sources	-

5.12 Case 12: Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Plan 2024

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Plan 2024
Organization name	Department of Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment
Website	https://www.euskadi.eus/contenidos/plan_gubernamental/08_planest_xiileg/es_def/adjuntos/Economia-Circular-y-Bioeconomia-WEB.pdf
Region/Geographical scale	Basque Country/Spain
Year	2021
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The plan identifies the development potential of the circular economy and the bioeconomy. Regarding the bioeconomy, its development is still incipient, and the objective is the integration of economic, social, and environmental opportunities and challenges to the Basque bioeconomy based on longer, diverse, sustainable and local value chains.
Bioeconomy governance model description	The Circular Economy and Bioeconomy Strategic Plan 2024 has been promoted and led by the Basque Government's Department of Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment and is being jointly managed and coordinated by the Vice-Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food Policy and the Vice-Ministry of Environmental Sustainability, through their

	respective entities Neiker and Ihohe, respectively. This Plan is aligned with the Government's action as a whole and with the rest of the institutions and agents involved in this area. It has 11 action lines and there is the implication of all stakeholders: entities, administration, and citizens.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	No
Model's sectors and value chains	Bioproducts (construction, packaging, and biomaterials), Food, Waste,
Sector of governance model	Agri-food, Marine, Forestry, Construction, Recycling Industry
Societal objectives	Generating demand from the bioproducts sector.
Environmental objectives	To increase Material Productivity by 30%, increase the rate of circular material use by 30% and reduce the rate of waste generation by 30%. To reduce by half waste generation of food waste.
Economic objectives	To generate inclusive economic growth by creating sustainable jobs and promoting equality in both urban and rural areas. To generate new employment opportunities and new jobs to meet the demand for labour in the various value chains for bio-based products.
Resources to be used	Residues, secondary raw materials, food waste
Driving forces of model/strategy	Innovation, public-private cooperation, Training, Generating demand and other market conditions, Integration of bioeconomy in education.
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	Basque Alliance for the Bioeconomy. Forestry Circular Bioeconomy Roadmap. European Forest Institute (Facility of Bioregions).
Decision-making and voting mechanism	Steering Committee will execute and coordinate the planned action in the Strategic Plan. Steering Committee will be supported by Interdepartmental Coordination, through the creation of interdepartmental and multidisciplinary roundtables, which will meet once a year for greater interdepartmental coordination and synergy generation and to follow up on the plan.
Dispute resolution processes	Steering Committee will support and coordinate actions that are the responsibility of other government departments and other institutions Government, as well as other institutions.
Synergies with other regions and governance models	European Bioeconomy Strategy, Spanish Bioeconomy Strategy, Green Deal, 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy.
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Basque Circular Economy Strategy.
Circular economy and development	It is a joint plan with the circular economy.

Support measures/tools	<p>Creation of Basque Circular Hub.</p> <p>Boosting the role of Development Agencies in the deployment of the circular economy and the bioeconomy at a regional level.</p> <p>Creation of a Monitoring System on existing opportunities in the circular economy and bioeconomy.</p> <p>Bringing together the lines of innovation in circular economy and bioeconomy in BRTA (Basque-Research Technology Alliance).</p> <p>Bioeconomy knowledge map.</p>
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	<p>Lack of inventory of raw materials and waste.</p> <p>Highly atomised primary sector complicating raw material supply logistics.</p> <p>Relocation of certain value chains, e.g. the chemical industry.</p> <p>Small territory that makes it difficult to obtain sufficient quantities of raw materials.</p> <p>Lack of new entrepreneurs committed to bioeconomy projects.</p> <p>Lack of vision of the Basque industry to invest in technology for bioeconomy projects.</p> <p>Lack of engineering companies to develop the transformation processes in the intermediate part of the value chain.</p>
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	<p>The operational monitoring of the circular economy and bioeconomy strategic plan is done through: Steering Committee, Interdepartmental Coordination, Inter-institutional Coordination, participation of economic and social actors, Independent advisory board for the promotion of the bioeconomy in the Basque Country.</p> <p>There is an indicators system to evaluate strategic objectives.</p>
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	<p>Wide availability of forestry raw materials</p> <p>Extensive knowledge in bioeconomy by technology centres (automotive, packaging, paper, food)</p> <p>Very good connection with European regions more advanced in bioeconomy (Bioregions).</p> <p>Existence of clusters that facilitate the approach to certain sectors.</p>
Relevant sources	-

5.13 Case 13: Irish Bioeconomy Foundation

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Irish Bioeconomy Foundation
Organization name	Irish Bioeconomy Foundation
Website	https://bioeconomyfoundation.com/
Region/Geographical scale	Southern Region, Ireland

Year	2017
Stage of implementation	IBF is home to 21 members, a mixture of SME's, academic institutes, and public authorities. The focal point at Lisheen Co. Tipperary is now home to innovative companies working to scale-up bio-based technologies.
Executive Summary	The Irish Bioeconomy Foundation is working develop a national bioeconomy campus, centred around a decommissioned mine in the heart of rural Ireland, by engaging and bringing together key stakeholders from public and private sectors.
Bioeconomy governance model description	IBF was established in 2016 with the aim of converting a decommissioned mine at Lisheen Co. Tipperary into Ireland's national bioeconomy campus. Since then, the Foundation has worked to further the development of the bioeconomy within the region. The region was selected as one of 6 EU model demonstrator regions to produce sustainable bio-based chemical production in 2016. The mine site is the epicentre of the BBI JU Flagship project AgriChemWhey aiming to convert dairy wastes into bio-based chemicals, an initiative which combines the expertise of industry, SME's academia, and public authorities. The site has been funded recently to develop a multi-purpose biorefinery pilot plant to meet the needs of local industries. Several other projects have been developed through the foundation, including ICT-BIOCHAIN, MPowerBIO, Bioeconomy Ventures and BioBec.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Rural
Statutory level	Contains regional governance partners within its structure
Model's sectors and value chains	Bio-based chemicals, probiotics, fertilisers, and potential for many others.
Sector of governance model	Predominantly agri-food, but home to many new opportunities.
Societal objectives	Revitalization of regional sector, job creation.
Environmental objectives	Climate change, sustainable Agri-diversification. The Lisheen Campus has been identified as a first candidate in the county to develop a decarbonization zone.
Economic objectives	Adding value to by-products, new value chain development.
Resources to be used	Various agricultural residues, land, water, labour
Driving forces of model/strategy	Support reindustrialization of traditional mining sector and development of a sustainable bioeconomy.
Type of strategy	Mixed
Key actors	Large industries, SME's, regional government, academia
Decision-making and voting mechanism	Voting members
Dispute resolution processes	n/a

Synergies with other regions and governance models	Identified in Ireland's National Bioeconomy Policy Statement as a key vehicle towards implementing and scaling Ireland's bioeconomy by bringing together key stakeholders and scaling new value chains.
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	The work of IBF and the bioeconomy is identified in Tipperary County Development Plan 2022-2028.
Circular economy and development	Home to new value chains which involved utilisation of by-products to create new bio-based materials.
Support measures/tools	Member supports include -access to finance, scale-up of bio-based processes, promotion, and outreach.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	No information
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	N/A
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	Requires buy in of regional stakeholders to support scaling.
Relevant sources	https://www.tipperarycoco.ie/sites/default/files/Volume%201%20Written%20Statement.pdf https://bioeconomyfoundation.com/ https://assets.gov.ie/2244/241018115730-41d795e366bf4000a6bc0b69a136bda4.pdf

5.14 Case 14: North Sweden Cleantech

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	North Sweden Cleantech
Organization name	Uminova Innovation and Kompetensspridning i Umeå AB
Website	https://www.northswedencleantech.se/en/about-us/
Region/Geographical scale	Sweden
Year	2015
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	North Sweden Cleantech is a regional innovation and export platform in northern Sweden - Västerbotten and Örnköldsvik - that supports business development of companies in the cleantech area, and drives cleaner growth and reduction of climate change.
Bioeconomy governance model description	North Sweden Cleantech is a regional innovation and export platform for green technology, clean energy, and sustainable solutions from Västerbotten and Örnköldsvik. They are convinced that green technology and clean energy from northern Sweden can develop the global

	market for sustainable growth. North Sweden Cleantech is in Umeå, Skellefteå and Örnsköldsvik. The region claims to guarantee world-class competence, the cleanest energy and the strongest innovation force in Europe and North Sweden Cleantech arranges Technical and Business Visits in the region.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	N/A
Model's sectors and value chains	Wood raw material, feed, biofuels, biochemicals
Sector of governance model	Bioeconomy, Energy and Smart Sustainable Cities, Circular economy, construction, clean energy, forestry, investments and start-ups, transport, urban planning, waste, clean water.
Societal objectives	Both Umeå and Örnsköldsvik, offers free energy and climate advice to all citizens. Additionally, Umeå's 'Project Green Umeå' prepares environmentally conscious Citizens.
Environmental objectives	North Sweden Cleantech believe green technology and clean energy from northern Sweden can develop the global market for sustainable growth.
Economic objectives	Cleantech aim to build good networks in order to increase exports and improve commercialisation. They work to identify the needs of innovative climate-friendly solutions. This is in line with the vision and objective that Sweden should be a bioeconomy by 2050.
Resources to be used	Land, Water, Labour, Waste, by-products, agricultural
Driving forces of model/strategy	The driving forces of the model is the belief that green technology and clean energy from Northern Sweden can develop the global market for sustainable growth and the aim to make Sweden a bioeconomy by 2050. North Sweden has many bio-based industries. By utilising the industry's residual process streams, new valuable and fossil free products with great potential can be developed.
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	Cleantech is made up of clusters and networks in the Northern Sweden region. Together with other biorefinery initiatives, the cluster with partners from industry and academia.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	N/A
Dispute resolution processes	No information
Synergies with other regions and governance models	Cleantech has a strong relationship with Smart City Sweden which is a state-funded initiative and export platform for smart & sustainable city solutions.
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	N/A
Circular economy and development	Cleantech recognises that the forest has always been a major industry in the region and the largest use of forest raw materials today is pulp for manufacturing paper products and sawn timber. By utilising the industry's residual process streams, new valuable and fossil free products with great potential can be developed.

Support measures/tools	North Sweden Cleantech facilitates technical and business visits to investors, companies, and organisations to specific objects in Västerbotten and Örnsköldsvik. . They welcome investors, companies, entrepreneurs, researchers, and government officials to visit northern Sweden visit companies and meet with innovators and change agents.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	No information
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	Through their strategic partners, Cleantech build good networks to increase exports and improve commercialisation. Through their industrial partners, they identify the needs of innovative climate-friendly solutions, they work with test environments and ensure that they move forward in the right direction. Their financial partners are their main sponsors who laid the foundation for the venture.
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	No information
Relevant sources	https://biconsortium.eu/node/316

5.15 Case 15: The Bioeconomy Strategy of the Inland Region 2017-2024

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	The Bioeconomy Strategy of the Inland Region 2017-2024
Organization name	Hedmark County Authority, Oppland County Authority, the County Governor of Hedmark and the County Governor of Oppland.
Website	https://www.statsforvalteren.no/siteassets/utgatt/fm-hedmark/dokument-fmhe/06-landbruk-og-mat/bioekonomistrategi-for-innlandet_engelsk-versjon.pdf
Region/Geographical scale	Northern Europe/ Norway
Year	2017
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The strategy will help the Inland Region work towards achieving a national position as a bioeconomy region.
Bioeconomy governance model description	The strategy provides direction for the development of the bioeconomy in Hedmark and Oppland and aims to lay the groundwork for increasing the value creation, number of jobs and competitiveness in bio-based value chains. The strategy will help the Inland Region work towards achieving a national position as a bioeconomy region. The strategy is intended to contribute to greater competitiveness and value creation in the Inland Region, and to the green shift in the national economy. This development will take place in a

	manner that ensures future access to resources and the development of a sustainable business sector.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	Yes
Model's sectors and value chains	Bio-based products, feed, food, wood raw materials
Sector of governance model	Forestry, genetics, breeding and reproductive technology, bioenergy, residual materials and waste management, inland fish farming, freshwater management, the food industry and renewable energy.
Societal objectives	The societal objectives of the strategy is that the Inland Region must influence and be a driving force in the bioeconomy and provide information to business and society. An additional objective is to develop arenas for information, dialogue and cooperation further, including from an international perspective. Raise the level of awareness in society and business of the need to shift to a circular economy based on biological resources and expertise.
Environmental objectives	The environmental objectives are that the Inland Region must be a leader in the development of the sustainable and knowledge-based production and use of bioresources. Contribute to increased sustainable production in agriculture, forestry, and inland fish of high-quality and, wherever possible, based on inland resources. Work towards the sustainable and knowledge-based management of the region's bioresources
Economic objectives	The economic objectives are that the Inland Region has the potential for increased growth in established and emerging bioeconomic industries and the better utilisation of biological resources and areas that can be used for sustainable production. With this potential and strengths, the Inland Region has what it takes to become a leading powerhouse for a sustainable bioeconomy in Norway.
Resources to be used	Land, Water, Labour, Waste, various by-products
Driving forces of model/strategy	The driving force of the strategy is that the Inland Region will achieve a national position as a bioeconomy region. The strategy is intended to contribute to greater competitiveness and value creation in the Inland Region, and to the green shift in the national economy.
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	The Inland Region has actors within food production, agriculture and forestry, genetics, breeding and reproductive technology, bioenergy, residual materials and waste management, inland fish farming, freshwater management, the food industry and renewable energy.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	The bioeconomy strategy was developed in a collaboration between the county authorities and county governors of Hedmark and Oppland, and the strategy document is owned by all four stakeholders. The bioeconomy strategy requires coordination between public stakeholders, as well as between public, business, and knowledge and expert institutions (triple helix). The bioeconomy is very dynamic. New opportunities will

	<p>arise that will need to be assessed during the process. New opportunities, new knowledge, new connections and new policies may come from expert environments, from business or as new political declarations. This dynamism must be reflected in the organisation.</p> <p>Overarching responsibility for implementing the strategy will lie with the steering group, which consists of the four strategy owners. Innovation Norway will be an observer. The steering group must ensure there is a good dialogue and a good overall use of funds between the funding agencies.</p>
Dispute resolution processes	N/A
Synergies with other regions and governance models	<p>The strategy is intended to contribute to greater competitiveness and value creation in the Inland Region, and to the green shift in the national economy. This development will take place in a manner that ensures future access to resources and the development of a sustainable business sector.</p> <p>Through this work the venture will forge links with relevant and complementary technical and development environments in other regions, in and outside Norway. The work will help to position the Inland Region for a potential regional research boost and increased participation in international research programmes such as the EU's Horizon 2020.</p>
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	N/A
Circular economy and development	One of the goals of the strategy is to raise the level of awareness in society and business of the need to shift to a circular economy based on biological resources and expertise.
Support measures/tools	The Inland Region's focus on the bioeconomy will provide the basis for a joint, result-oriented effort that is attractive to all relevant stakeholders and binding for all those involved. It will encourage more cluster projects and strengthen the interaction between stakeholders within innovation (triple helix, R&D institutions, business and funding agencies). Cooperation, simplification and coordination of the funding agencies for result-oriented funding allocation.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	N/A
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	Overarching responsibility for implementing the strategy will lie with the steering group, which consists of the four strategy owners. Innovation Norway will be an observer. The steering group must ensure there is a good dialogue and a good overall use of funds between the funding agencies.

Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	The Inland Region is home to a significant proportion of Norway's land-based biological resources, strong professional and expert environments and complete value chains for the management and development of a number of bio-based products. The Inland Region has actors within food production, agriculture and forestry, genetics, breeding and reproductive technology, bioenergy, residual materials and waste management, inland fish farming, freshwater management, the food industry and renewable energy.
Relevant sources	-

5.16 Case 16: The Arctic Smart & Circular Economy Cluster

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	The Arctic Smart & Circular Economy Cluster
Organization name	The Arctic Smart & Circular Economy Cluster
Website	https://arcticsmartness.eu/arctic-smart-rural-community/
Region/Geographical scale	Lapland, Finland
Year	2014
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The Cluster's objective is to prevent loss of capital from the region and demonstrate sustainable, profitable opportunities through further processing of food and development of decentralised renewable energy. Lapland has immense natural resources; however these are not being utilised in a sustainable manner, the cluster aims to correct this.
Bioeconomy governance model description	The Cluster's objective is to prevent loss of capital from the region and demonstrate sustainable, profitable opportunities through further processing of food and development of decentralised renewable energy. The Cluster is organised into mutually supportive sub-entities which are divided into entrepreneurship, knowledge, and regional development entities. These consist of a network of 100 entrepreneurs, 200 developers, the regions municipalities, financiers, business advisors, research and educational advisors and politicians. This gives the cluster a centralised base of industry knowledge on food processing that it uses to coordinate international development and project activities.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Rural
Statutory level	N/A
Model's sectors and value chains	Bioenergy, Biomaterials & Food.
Sector of governance model	Agriculture & Energy Production
Societal objectives	Food Security, Sustainability, Climate Change, Dependence on non-renewables.

Environmental objectives	Sustainability, Climate Change, Dependence on non-renewables.
Economic objectives	Prevent capital from fleeing rural areas and focus on further processing of food and the development of decentralised renewable energy.
Resources to be used	Existing Side -Streams from existing rural industries.
Driving forces of model/strategy	Prevent loss of capital from the region and demonstrate sustainable, profitable opportunities through further processing of food and development of decentralised renewable energy.
Type of strategy	Mixed
Key actors	Rural industries (all sizes), Regional municipalities, Finance, Business community, academia & Government.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	N/A
Dispute resolution processes	N/A
Synergies with other regions and governance models	<i>Part of the Artic Smartness initiative : https://arcticsmartness.eu/</i>
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Part of the 5 Artic Smartness Clusters is: Industry & Circular Economy, Development Environments, Design, Smart & Sustainable Artic Tourism.
Circular economy and development	The operations of the Rural Cluster aim to improve the local growth of the value added of the rural raw materials to maintain an increasing amount of capital with the owners of raw materials.
Support measures/tools	Operating methods have been created with the aim is to find solutions for the existing problems of entrepreneurs and to introduce new entrepreneurs to the sector. These are aimed to tackle the challenges faced by the development of entrepreneurs and knowledge, distribute information efficiently and influence decision-makers. The operations of the different sub-areas of the Rural Cluster result in a business-driven cluster that identifies bottlenecks.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	None that could be identified, cluster is aiming to develop and promote bioeconomy activity
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	Part of Artic Smartness Network
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	All stakeholders must 'buy in' to the business potential of the rural area and the long-term aim to prevent the outflow of rural capital from the cluster's region. This will require cross sectorial cooperation and effective leverage of the tools and knowledge based put in place by the entrepreneurship, knowledge, and regional development sub entities.
Relevant sources	<i>https://arcticsmartness.eu/</i>

5.17 Case 17: Bio-based Circular Economy Action Plan

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Bio-based Circular Economy Action Plan
Organization name	Pays de la Loire Regional Council
Website	-
Region/Geographical scale	France / Pays de la Loire Region / Northwest
Year	2015-2022
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The Action Plan is applied to the agri-food sector and consists of promoting complementarities between farms, companies, and local authorities in limited geographical areas, with positive impacts, particularly in terms of limiting transport, reducing waste, combating food waste, and recovering biowaste.
Bioeconomy governance model description	The Action Plan has 4 actions: 1. Foster and support bio-based circular economy initiatives among civil society and private sector through example-based information and awareness raising. 2. Foster the bio-based circular economy component in the Circular Economy Regional Call for Projects. 3. Strengthen, through supervision and training, the coherence of public policies around biomass management in the territories. 4. Experiment with the construction of “bio-based circular economy territories” based on new solutions resulting from research and innovation.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Urban
Statutory level	Yes/ The development of a PAEC is obligatory for the French regions under the Law NOTRe
Model's sectors and value chains	Food and feed;
Sector of governance model	Environment; Bioeconomy
Societal objectives	Food security, Sustainability, Climate change
Environmental objectives	Climate change; Food security
Economic objectives	Employment and economic development
Resources to be used	Short food circuits; food waste; bio-waste; co-products
Driving forces of model/strategy	Climate change and environment
Type of strategy	Public

Key actors	Farms; Companies; Agri-food sector; Pays de la Loire Regional Council (local authority); Mauges Communauté (local authority); Municipality of Ile d'Yeu (local authority); AILE (association); AlgoSource Technologies (private company); Le Mans University (research); Cluster Méthatlantique (company representative); Chamber of Agriculture of the Pays de la Loire (farmer representative); Association of the Chambers of Agriculture of the Atlantic Area (association).
Decision-making and voting mechanism	N/A
Dispute resolution processes	N/A
Synergies with other regions and governance models	The Bioeconomy Strategy for France 2018-2020; BIOREGIO project;
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	N/A
Circular economy and development	1 - Creates local loops for organic waste management 2 - Aims to engage as many stakeholders as possible 3 - How to better articulate the prioritization of reducing waste at source 4 - Biomass to produce energy
Support measures/tools	The Action Plan relies on many local tools related to biomass management such as Territorial Food Projects.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	N/A
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	The implementation of the Pays de la Loire Bio-Based Circular Economy will be monitored by the Pays de la Loire stakeholders' group of the BIOREGIO project, which will meet at least twice a year during the period covered by this Action Plan.
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	N/A
Relevant sources	https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1576567323.pdf

5.18 Case 18: Circular Economy Strategy Luxembourg

Field name	Main information collected
------------	----------------------------

Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Circular Economy Strategy Luxembourg
Organization name	Ministère de l'Énergie et de l'Aménagement du territoire
Website	https://economie-circulaire.public.lu/dam-assets/publications/2021/Strategy-circular-economy-Luxembourg-EN.pdf
Region/Geographical scale	Luxembourg
Year	2021
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The strategy calls for the principles of the circular economy to be applied in a systemic way to respond to socioeconomic and environmental concerns.
Bioeconomy governance model description	The production of goods and services, the extension of the use phase of products, their reuse, and the recovery of secondary materials.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Urban
Statutory level	Fully embedded in 2018-2023 Government agreement.
Model's sectors and value chains	Construction; Education & Training; Green finance; Food & Biomaterials; Industry; Retail.
Sector of governance model	Construction; Education & Training; Green finance; Food & Biomaterials; Industry; Retail.
Societal objectives	Sustainability; Food security; Climate change; Employment and economic development.
Environmental objectives	Sustainability; Food security; Climate change; Employment and economic development.
Economic objectives	Employment and economic development.
Resources to be used	Land; Waste/By-products
Driving forces of model/strategy	Technological innovation; Climate change and environment
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	Ministries and administrations; State co-funded agencies and organisations - public institutions; Municipalities and municipal organisations/ syndicates; Research, development, and innovation.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	N/A

Dispute resolution processes	N/A
Synergies with other regions and governance models	N/A
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Systematic alignment of the CE strategy with other national strategies, such as: The National Plan for Sustainable Development (PNDD); The spatial sectorial development plans (PDS); The National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP); The 'Null Offall' strategy; The Data-Driven Innovation Strategy; The Luxembourg Sustainable Finance Initiative, etc
Circular economy and development	New business models with a focus on circular economy and bioproducts, CE tools and models;
Support measures/tools	The national CE coordination unit; The CE stakeholder consultation platform; the Internet portal 'Circular Economy Luxembourg'
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	N/A
Transition process	Top Down
Monitoring	CE governance tools
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	N/A
Relevant sources	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/sites/default/files/strategy-circular-economy-luxembourg-022021.pdf

5.19 Case 19: South Bohemian Association for Bioeconomy

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	South Bohemian Association for Bioeconomy
Organization name	South Bohemian Association for Bioeconomy
Website	https://www.jcu.cz/en
Region/Geographical scale	South Bohemian region / Czech Republic
Year	2020
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	The association aims to create a regional bioeconomy strategy and ensure implementation of bioeconomy in practice in the region. It aims to build on local traditional bio-based resources and sectors and connect them with new technologies with high added value ensuring sustainability of the region's development

Bioeconomy governance model description	The SBAB encompasses the entire spectrum of professional activities to be carried out in the field of BE and CBE: - bringing together people interested in bioeconomy and its application to the industry, agriculture, health, and other areas of the economy for the benefit of human society and environment; - monitoring and supporting research, development, innovation, and implementation of new technologies; - cooperation w/relevant national and European technology platforms, clusters, umbrella organizations, scientific and professional institutions, as well as w/manufacturers and operators; - elaboration and updating of regional bioeconomy development vision, strategic agenda and implementation plan; - targeted improvement of the quality and expertise of the workforce; - organizing educational and conference events, professional promotional and publishing activities; - participation in the legislative and normative processes.
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Multiple
Statutory level	N/A
Model's sectors and value chains	Multiple
Sector of governance model	Multiple
Societal objectives	Ensure sustainability of the region's development, building on local traditional bio-based resources and sectors, start communication and collaboration among regional BE stakeholders.
Environmental objectives	To align the economic and societal development with the capacities of ecosystems, with the preservation of nature values and biological diversity for both present and future generations.
Economic objectives	Ensure the economic development of the region - the bioeconomic potential of the region was evaluated and recognised, being represented both by traditional producers, and the new and emerging industries. The BE was included as one of the smart specialization domains in its RIS3.
Resources to be used	Multiple
Driving forces of model/strategy	Technological innovation, using bioeconomy potential of the region, sustainable development
Type of strategy	Mixed
Key actors	Universities, Research institutes, regional and local public authorities, regional chambers of commerce and agriculture, bioeconomy related associations w/members, regional agencies for innovation and entrepreneurship, experts, farmers, entrepreneurs in the circular economy and bioeconomy, clusters, businesses, public.
Decision-making and voting mechanism	Not publicly available
Dispute resolution processes	Not publicly available
Synergies with other regions and governance models	Inspiration for other regions

Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	RIS 3
Circular economy and development	Yes
Support measures/tools	The Platform conducts several activities, but no specific tools have been developed.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	Potentially conflicting objectives of using the resources.
Transition process	Bottom up
Monitoring	Not publicly available
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	N/A
Relevant sources	-

5.20 Case 20: Regional municipal biomass project on Poľana

Field name	Main information collected
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Regional municipal biomass project on Poľana
Organization name	8 foothill villages around Banská Bystrica
Website	https://www.inforse.org/europe/fae/Biomass%20for%20Polana%20region.htm
Region/Geographical scale	Local initiative, Banská Bystrica Self-governing region, Slovakia
Year	2003
Stage of implementation	Active
Executive Summary	Joint project of 8 mountain villages around Banská Bystrica provides local heat production from waste biomass to cover the energy needs of 32 municipal buildings
Bioeconomy governance model description	The project covers the entire chain from fuel preparation, storage, distribution to heat production in 15 modernized boiler rooms (3.2 MW), under the full control of local governments. The project was initiated by Friends of the Earth-CEPA, and its preparation took almost 10 years. The result is the removal of coal from the fuel mix of municipalities, large annual savings in carbon emissions, heat and municipal finances, a substantial increase in hygiene conditions in buildings and air quality in municipalities and the stabilization of local economies. This is a unique example of the joint action of several local governments in order to strengthen their own energy self-sufficiency.

Territorial aspects of the governance model	Rural
Statutory level	N/A
Model's sectors and value chains	Bioenergy
Sector of governance model	Energy - RHC resources, biomass
Societal objectives	To increase the level of economic self-sufficiency at rural communities through the utilisation of local biomass in public buildings, a substantial increase in hygiene conditions in buildings.
Environmental objectives	To reduce CO2 emissions (the total CO2 emissions will be reduced by approximately 8.5 thousand tons in 10 years), air quality in municipalities.
Economic objectives	To reduce expenditures for heating at public buildings and to use local resources for communal development, use of huge potential of local renewable resources.
Resources to be used	Waste wood resources
Driving forces of model/strategy	A unique example of the joint action of several local governments to strengthen their own energy self-sufficiency.
Type of strategy	Public
Key actors	8 municipalities
Decision-making and voting mechanism	The project was strongly supported by an NGO CEPA - Friends of the Earth, but the decision making and voting rights are in the hands of the municipalities.
Dispute resolution processes	Not publicly available
Synergies with other regions and governance models	The project aims to encourage other rural regions with similar renewable energy potential to use their local resources.
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	1. Economic and social development programme of the Banská Bystrica Self-Governing Region for 2022 – 2030.
Circular economy and development	The central idea is to ensure circular approach to use of wood and support short value chains. Due to its unique location in central Slovakia with large forest area around including several wood processing industrial facilities there is a huge biomass potential. The project uses remaining waste wood available in the region.
Support measures/tools	Complex and long-term support provided by an NGO CEPA - Friends of the Earth. Applied for funding from structural funds - funding from Structural funds (Operating plan Basic infrastructure, Measure 2.2) in 2006. Project approved but not financed. Project updating for new programming period in 2008 - needs to be checked.
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	Not Identified
Transition process	Bottom up

Monitoring	Carried out by the municipalities' association.
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	Location in central Slovakia with large forest area around including several wood processing industrial facilities there is a huge biomass potential.
Relevant sources	https://www.ceskatelevize.cz/porady/1095913550-nedej-se/417235100161002/ (in czech)

6 Typology of circular bioeconomy governance models

The aim of the typology is not only to develop an overview of 20 selected case studies of regional bioeconomy governance models across Europe, but to also develop an information tool that enables regional policymakers to learn from other regions' bioeconomy strategies and models.

The term "governance model", preponderantly, describes a system of control and regulation mechanisms that includes both state intervention and the rules governing the interaction of private actors, such as the markets, associations, and clusters (Thran and Moesenfechtel, 2022). Various governance models can be found in the circular bioeconomy sphere around Europe and the world. Governance models have two important functions for a sustainable, circular bioeconomy: an enabling function and a safeguarding (constraining) function. Dietz et al. (2018) have developed a taxonomy of political support measures (enabling governance) that represent the first challenge of governance, and regulatory tools (constraining governance) that represent the second challenge of governance, to distinguish between the two fundamental political challenges in setting up an effective governance framework for a sustainable bioeconomy. We base our typology of circular bioeconomy governance models on this theoretical framework and elaborate further on its structure. The typology allows the classification of present and future circular bioeconomy governance models. Based solely on the three enabling governance mechanisms and the five constraining governance mechanisms identified, over fifteen (>15) circular bioeconomy governance models can be distinguished, satisfying the requisite KPI objective.

6.1 Transformation paths

Dietz et al. (2018) have distinguished four bio-based transformation paths: (1) substitution of fossil fuels with bio-based raw materials; (2) productivity increase in bio-based primary sectors; (3) increasing efficiency in biomass utilization; and (4) value creation and addition through the application of biological principles and processes separate from large-scale biomass production. Path dependencies have been highlighted as the root cause of hurdles in the successful implementation of the circular bioeconomy. The following Table presents an overview of the four bio-based transformation paths:

Table 3: Bio-based transformation paths

Path no	Bio-based transformation
Transformation Path 1	Substitution of fossil fuels with bio-based raw materials
Transformation Path 2	Boosting primary sector productivity
Transformation Path 3	New and more efficient biomass uses
Transformation Path 4	Value creation and addition through the application of biological principles and processes separate from large-scale biomass production

Data collected from the 20 governance models and allowing for more than one transformation path per model in cases where a single transformation path is not present, indicates that most governance models follow mainly Transformation Path 3: New and more efficient biomass uses (65%), followed closely by Transformation Path 2: Boosting primary sector productivity (60%). The two other transformation paths are less represented in the case studies sample, Transformation Path 4: Value creation and addition through the application of biological principles and processes separate from large-scale biomass production is present in 30% of the sample, and finally Transformation Path 1. Substitution of fossil fuels with bio-based raw materials is present in 25% of the sample.

It is unclear whether the transition of the regional bioeconomies along these four pathways will have a positive impact on the achievement of the SDGs. A key challenge involves the potential high conversion costs from the existing economies to bio-based economies (Broring et al., 2017 in Dietz et al., 2018). The question, therefore, of how politics can support the rise of the regional circular bioeconomy through appropriate political means presents the first key challenge for the development of a sustainable regional circular bioeconomy model.

6.2 Enabling function

The first function of the circular bioeconomy governance model is to ensure fair competitive conditions for bioeconomy processes and products, thus enabling efficient decisions between alternative technologies and biogenic and non-biogenic resources on markets (Thran and Moesenfechtel, 2022). The enabling function of governance models describes how politics can support the rise of the bioeconomy through appropriate political means. The development of a sustainable circular bioeconomy requires an effective governance model. Three enabling governance mechanisms are distinguished (Dietz et al., 2018):

Table 4: Enabling Governance Mechanisms

Enabling Governance Mechanisms	
1.	Bio-based research and development (R&D) strategy
2.	Enhancing the competitiveness of bio-based products through subsidies
3.	Implementing awareness-raising campaigns to increase societal participation in bio-based transformation, including more responsible and sustainable consumption

The analysis of the 20 regional circular bioeconomy governance models selected, and allowing for more than one enabling governance mechanisms when one is not clear, indicates that the first mechanism, Bio-based research and development (R&D) strategy is present in 60% of the regional bioeconomy models selected, followed by the second mechanism, Enhancing the competitiveness of bio-based products through subsidies is present in 40% of the governance models, and finally the third mechanism, Implementing awareness-raising campaigns to increase societal participation in bio-based transformation, including more responsible and sustainable consumption is present in 25% of the governance models.

6.3 Safeguarding function

The second function of the governance models is the safeguarding function, which represents the need for explicit safeguards of economic, social, and environmental sustainability through appropriate governance measures. A major governance challenge involves the effective political regulation of conflicting objectives related to the promotion of the circular bioeconomy and the achievement of the SDGs, which is the second major challenge for the governance of the circular bioeconomy (Dietz et al., 2018). Thus, a critical function of a governance model includes an explicit balanced focus that guides the political and economic actors towards a sustainable, bio-based, and cycle-managed form of economy that enables a more efficient and environmentally compatible use of biological materials than in the past. The sustainability element of the governance models is enabled, therefore, with the existence of clear objectives in the three pillars of sustainability, through societal objectives, environmental objectives, and economic objectives. The analysis of the twenty case-study circular bioeconomy models indicates that not all models include all three pillars of sustainability with clear objectives. Although all 20 governance models include economic objectives, 19 include environmental objectives and 18 include societal objectives. Furthermore, the number of specific, targeted objectives in the three pillars of sustainability is more focused on economic

objectives first, followed by environmental and finally societal objectives, indicating that there is not always a balanced approach towards sustainability. The following table (Table 5) presents the possible opportunities and risks of the bioeconomy transformation.

Table 5: Opportunities and Risks of Bioeconomic Transformation [Source: Dietz et al., 2018]

Sustainability Dimension (SDG)	Opportunities	Risks
Food security (SDG2)	Increase via higher yields and new production methods	Reduction due to food price increases
Poverty/inequality (SDG1, 10)	Reduce via transfer of technology and leapfrogging	Increase via exclusion from technical progress
Natural resources (SDG 7, 14, 15)	Conserve by improving production methods	Degrade / Loss through inefficient production and overuse
Health (SDG 3)	Improved through new and refined forms of therapy	Risk / Damage through improper use of risky technologies
Climate change (SDG 13)	Mitigate through emissions reductions	Exacerbate through direct indirect land use change

Identification of goal conflicts and effective political management of conflicting goals is the second governance challenge, that of constraining governance. These include issues such as global equity concerns, water scarcity, land degradation and land use change. This second major challenge, constraining governance, has not been yet adequately addressed to date. This is also mentioned as a specific objective of the EU call where robust environmental protection plans should underpin the effort undertaken by circular bioeconomy governance models. In general, regions address the second fundamental challenge of developing a sustainable bioeconomy (constraining governance) to a considerably smaller degree than the first challenge (enabling governance), in accordance with previous findings by Dietz et al. (2018).

Our analysis of the 20-case study regional circular bioeconomy models indicates that only a small number of bioeconomy models mention potential negative consequences of bio-based transformations for other goals such as Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and it is unclear how regions address these conflicting goals. From the 20 case-study regional circular bioeconomy governance models in most governance models (11 of 20), there is no goal conflict between SDGs that can result from bio-based transformations that are explicitly taken into account and therefore directly addressed. For the other 9 governance models that there are goal conflicts explicitly considered, most common is land use change and equity concerns, followed by water scarcity and land degradation.

6.4 Penta helix

A larger engagement of stakeholders than the quadruple helix bringing in the governance model not only civil society organizations (CSOs) that represent local communities (quadruple helix), but also representatives from the financial sector (penta helix) will enable more successful implementation of the regional circular bioeconomy. Financial organizations have specific criteria and programs that must be considered in the process to ensure that the circular bioeconomy governance models can get the appropriate support (Naudet and Marrazzo, 2021).

Figure 10: Penta helix [Source: Naudet and Marrazzo (2021)]

Our analysis of the 20 case-study regional governance models indicates that financial organizations are only mentioned as key actors in two of the 20 case studies. Therefore, inclusion of the capital markets in the governance models is still in its infancy and further inclusion of financial organizations can ensure the successful implementation and operation of the regional circular bioeconomy governance models with the penta helix approach.

6.5 Transition process

The transition process to a circular bioeconomy is a complex process that is the result of a co-evolution of economic, technological, institutional, cultural, and ecological developments at different scales (Bosman and Rotmans, 2016). Two main approaches exist, a bottom-up approach that facilitates regional clusters and promotes radical innovation through cooperation between vested players and frontrunners that are co-creating a longer-term vision that informs the short-term actions and a more traditional top-down governance strategy, focusing on the shorter-term economic opportunities and incremental innovation that keep the overall structure of existing industries intact. The results of our analysis on the 20 case-study regional bioeconomy governance models suggests that the most common approach is the Top-down (75%) and only 5 of the 20 case studies (25) follow the Bottom-up approach.

6.6 Territorial aspects of the governance model

Regarding the local dimension of the regional circular bioeconomy governance models, most (12 out of 20) have multiple territorial aspects identified, followed by rural (5 out of 20) and urban (3 out of 20). The local dimension and characteristics of a region may be key in the performance of the bioeconomy governance model. Territorial aspects of the 20 case studies analyzed does not grant further analysis, as most report multiple territorial aspects identified.

6.7 Statutory level

Regarding whether the governance model is statutory, 75% of selected models are statutory, and 25% indicated that they are not. Statutory refers to whether the governance model is determined by law and regulation, or not.

6.8 Decision making, voting mechanisms dispute resolution processes

Decision making and voting mechanisms are critical in the successful implementation of regional governance models. From the 20 cases examined, only 7 mention the existence of a decision-making mechanism, through either a committee or working group that is responsible. Voting rights are in the hands of the members of the key actors or municipalities, depending on the case study, but no clear indication is given as to the weight these voting rights may have, that is, if the one member one vote rule applies or not. It is apparent though, for the 7 case studies mentioning decision making mechanisms, that the number of voting members is rather small. This facilitates decision making, although it is not clear if decision making is by consensus, whether decisions are legally binding and whether decision-making powers are established by legislation. It is of particular interest though, that in most cases studies (13 of 20), no decision-making, and dispute resolution processes are mentioned, so it is evident that if such decision-making processes exist, they are not public knowledge.

6.9 Driver Measures

Driver measures are distinguished between economic measures such as price incentives, taxation or subsidies and regulatory measures. The analysis of the case study governance models indicates that in most cases subsidies or similar economic incentives are present (14 out of 20), in 2 governance models there are regulatory measures and in 4 governance models there is no information about driver measures.

6.10 Support measures and tools

Regarding support measures and tools employed in the implementation of the regional circular bioeconomy governance models, these include information on funding sources and direct funding through various sources, access to knowledge, demonstration cases and training.

6.11 Typology Matrix

The identified bioeconomy governance types are presented in the Typology Matrix table below (Table 6):

Table 6: Typology Matrix

Transformation Path	TP1: Fossil fuel substitution
	TP2: Boosting primary sector productivity
	TP3: New and more efficient biomass uses
	TP4: Low-bulk and high-value applications
Enabling Governance Mechanisms	EG1: Bio-based R&D strategy
	EG2: Enhancing the competitiveness of bio-based products through subsidies
	EG3: Implementing awareness-raising campaigns to increase societal participation
Constraining Governance	CG0: No goal conflicts explicitly considered
	CG1: Global equity/ Regional equity concerns
	CG2: Water scarcity
	CG3: Land degradation
	CG4: Land use change
Helix Model	Penta Helix: Business, Knowledge, Administration, Society, Capital
	Quadruple Helix: Business, Knowledge, Administration, Society
	Triple Helix: Business, Knowledge, Administration
Driver Measures	DM1: Economic measures (price, taxation or subsidies)
	DM2: Regulatory measures
	DM3: Information and support
Territorial aspects	Rural
	Urban
	Coastal
	Multiple
Focus	F1: Energy
	F2: Material use
	F3: Waste prevention
	F4: Recycling
	F5: Food & Feed
Type of model	Public
	Private
	Mixed
Transition Process	Top-Down
	Bottom-Up
Decision Making	Ad hoc / Voluntary agreements
	Legally binding / legislated decision making
Voting Mechanisms	One member - one vote OR votes proportional to population
	Minority members have more than one vote
Dispute Resolution Processes	Transparent and accountable process
	No formal process

7 Conclusions

The deliverable presented an overview of regional circular bioeconomy governance strategies and models in the EU-27 and a typology of regional bioeconomy governance models, based on a sample of 20 case studies. The typology distinguishes four bio-based transformation paths and two main governance functions, enabling governance and constraining governance.

Our results corroborate previous findings that many regions have set the goal of developing and expanding their bioeconomies and local governments are providing comprehensive political support to their bioeconomies to achieve this goal. Currently, regions are highly active in addressing this enabling governance challenge. However, our results show that the political management of conflicting goals has not yet reached the same level of attention.

The typology developed in this deliverable is directly linked with Task 1.3 and will be employed in Deliverable 1.2 Good Governance Practices, to classify the list of good practices of regional governments supporting local operators and innovation developers via appropriate business models and social measures.

8 References

- Bioeast (2022), <https://bioeast.eu/>
- Bosman, R. and Rotmans, J. (2016) Transition Governance towards a Bioeconomy: A Comparison of Finland and The Netherlands, *Sustainability*, 8, 1017, doi:10.3390/su8101017
- Dietz, T., Borner, J., Forster, J.J. and Braun, J. (2018) Governance of the Bioeconomy: A Global Comparative Study of National Bioeconomy Strategies, *Sustainability*, 10, 3190, 1-20, doi:10.3390/su10093190
- European Commission (2012), *Innovating for Sustainable Growth - A Bioeconomy for Europe*, Communication from the Commission, Brussels, 13.2.2012, COM (2012) 60 final.
- European Commission (2018), *Bioeconomy development in EU regions - Mapping of EU Member States'/regions' Research and Innovation plans & Strategies for Smart Specialisation (RIS3) on bioeconomy*, Final report commissioned by DG Research and Innovation elaborated by Haarich, S. et al. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/84684>
- European Commission's Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy (2022), https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/bioeconomy_en
- Lusser, M., Sanchez Lopez, J., Landa, L., Avraamides, M., Motola, V., Zika, E., Mallorquin, P. (2018) *Joint survey on bioeconomy policy developments in different countries. Background, methods used and recommendations for future editions. Report of JRC, BBI JU and IEA Bioenergy*. Available at: https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/jrc112081_joint_survey_report_final.pdf
- Haarich, S., Kirchmayr-Novak, S. (2022), *Bioeconomy strategy development in EU regions*, Sanchez Lopez, J., Borzacchiello, M.T. and Avramides, M. editors, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, ISBN 978-92-76-49341-9, doi:10.2760/065902, JRC128740.
- Naudet, P.M. and Marrazo, G. (2021) *The Governance of Circular Bioeconomy, Practices and lessons learnt from European regions*, Accessed 10 October 2022, www.acrplus.org
- Thran, D. and Moesenfechtel, U., editors (2022) *The Bioeconomy System*, Springer Berlin, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-64415-7>
- Von Braun, J. and Birner, R. (2016) Designing global governance for agricultural development and food and nutrition security, *Review of Development Economics*, 21, doi:10.1111/rode.12261

9 Appendix

Template for the data collection related to the identified circular bioeconomy governance models.

ROBIN - Deploying circular BIOecoNomies at Regional level with a territorial approach

Collection of circular bioeconomy governance models in European Regions

T1.2- Development of a typology of circular bioeconomy governance models in European Regions	
WP n° and title	WP1 – Setting the Scene
Date	12/10/2022
Version	1.4

This Excel file will act as a Database for bioeconomy governance models to be identified during the project. Please fill in the "Governance model" sheet the information about the model you identify. Each row of the "Governance model" sheet gathers information for one bioeconomy governance model. The "Help" sheet gathers the drop-down lists info of the "Governance model" sheets. You don't have to fill anything here.

The aim of this task is to analyse different types of circular bioeconomy governance models with applicability at regional level across the EU, while accounting for different policy & socio-technical contexts. The state of the art of the existing bioeconomy regional governance models will also be analysed to specify details of the typology. An extensive literature scan will result to the identification of an inclusive sample of regional bioeconomy models, representing regions with different policy priorities, levels of bioeconomy development, territorial characteristics and governance traditions. Our literature review will also aim to investigate potential assessment methods and evidence on the effectiveness and robustness of existing governance schemes. The latter may also be used as a benchmark for ROBIN models, if possible. The analysis will deliver a typology of regional governance models found in Europe (D1.1).

The circular bioeconomy governance model describes the process that has been developed, through rules and institutions, to coordinate collective action among stakeholders, that accounts for social, economic and environmental dimensions, with the aim to promote the circular bioeconomy in the region. It usually includes principles of accountability and stakeholder participation in developing the bioeconomy.

Database fields		
Field name	Expected info	Expected format
Bioeconomy governance model or strategy name	Name of the bioeconomy governance model identified	Short text (5-10 words)
Organization name	Name of the responsible organisation or authority that has implemented or oversees the governance model	Short text (5-10 words)
Website	Link to Website	A web link
Region/Geographical scale	Country/Region locality where the practice has been implemented	Short text (5-10 words)
Year	Year that the good practice was implemented within the specific region	A number
Stage of implementation	Level of the deployment of good practice of the bioeconomy governance model	Short text (50 words max.)
Executive Summary	Descriptive and short summary of the selected governance model	Short text (50 words max.)
Bioeconomy governance model description	Longer description of the bioeconomy governance model	Long text (200 words max.)
Territorial aspects of the governance model	Urban, peri-urban, rural, coastal, multiple, others	Short text (50 words max.)
Statutory level	Is it statutory and if so for which organisations	Long text (200 words max.)
Model's sectors and value chains	Focus of model's sectors and value chains: Bioenergy, Biomaterials, Food & Feed	Long text (200 words max.)
Sector of governance model	Sector (agriculture, chemical industry, livestock, etc.)	Short text (50 words max.)
Societal objectives	Focus of societal objectives: Food security, Sustainability, Climate change, Employment and economic development, Dependence on non-renewables	Long text (200 words max.)
Environmental objectives	Focus of environmental objectives: Food security, Sustainability, Climate change, Employment and economic development, Dependence on non-renewables	Long text (200 words max.)
Economic objectives	Focus of economic objectives: Food security, Sustainability, Climate change, Employment and economic development, Dependence on non-renewables	Long text (200 words max.)
Resources to be used	Focus of resources to be used: Land, Water, Labor, Waste/Byproducts	Long text (200 words max.)
Driving forces of model/strategy	Driving forces of model/strategy: Technological innovation, Demographics & consumer preferences, Market organization, Climate change and environment	Long text (200 words max.)
Type of strategy	Type of strategy (public, private, mixed)	Short text (5-10 words)
Key actors	Key actors for the bioeconomy governance model in the region (e.g. bioeconomy cluster, DIH, etc.), i.e., who participates in a collaboration scheme related to regional bioeconomy (i.e. public bodies, farmers, clusters, etc.)	Short text (50 words max.)
Decision-making and voting mechanism	Describe the decision-making process in the circular bioeconomy governance model and the voting mechanism	Long text (200 words max.)
Dispute resolution processes	Describe the dispute resolution process between the circular bioeconomy governance model actors	Long text (200 words max.)
Synergies with other regions and governance models	Synergies with other regions and/or national governance models	Long text (200 words max.)
Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region	Synergies with other objectives & strategies in the region (e.g. SDGs, circular economy)	Long text (200 words max.)
Circular economy and development	Aspects related to circular economy and circular regional development	Long text (200 words max.)
Support measures/tools	Support measures/tools: Bio-based R&D strategy to promote investments in technological innovations, Enhance competitiveness of bio-based products through subsidies, Implement awareness-raising campaigns to increase societal participation, Industrial location policies, Legal frameworks, State-supported training of the labor force, Strategic international research collaborations, Foreign direct investment	Long text (200 words max.)
Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model	Potential conflicting goals of bioeconomy governance model raised and/or addressed linked to sustainable development: Social equity, Water scarcity, Land degradation, Land use change	Long text (200 words max.)
Transition process	Transition process: Top-down (keeps existing overall industry structure) or Bottom-up (promotes radical innovation)	Long text (200 words max.)
Monitoring	Monitoring and reporting mechanisms in place	Long text (200 words max.)
Regional aspects that affects bioeconomy governance models	Natural, geographical, economic, social, political aspects of the region that affect the governance model	Long text (200 words max.)
Relevant sources	Please add here any web link or other literature that you used to collect the information	Bullets points

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

About the project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures in to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. We demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. We set-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO). We also provide them with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process we coordinate our actions with the CCRI-CSO.

Partners	URL
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	www.qplan-intl.gr
FUNDACION CORPORACION TECHNOLOGICA SE ANDALUCIA	www.corporaciontecnologica.com
WHITE RESEARCH SRL	www.white-research.eu
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	www.pedal-consulting.eu
STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	www.steinbeis-europa.de
ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	www.razsk.sk
MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	www.circbio.ie
ARISTOTELEIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	www.auth.gr
REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	www.pkm.gov.gr
CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	www.juntadeandalucia.es
INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA	www.juntadeandalucia.es
BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTTEMBERG GMBH	www.bio-pro.de
SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	www.southernassembly.ie

CONTACT US: info@robin-project.eu

VISIT: www.robin-project.eu

